

On the Correctness of Monadic Backward Induction

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Abstract

In control theory, to solve a finite-horizon sequential decision problem (SDP) commonly means to find a list of decision rules that result in an optimal expected total reward (or cost) when taking a given number of decision steps. SDPs are routinely solved using Bellman's backward induction. Textbook authors (e.g. Bertsekas or Puterman) typically give more or less formal proofs to show that the backward induction algorithm is correct as solution method for deterministic and stochastic SDPs.

Botta, Jansson and Ionescu propose a generic framework for finite horizon, *monadic* SDPs together with a monadic version of backward induction for solving such SDPs. In monadic SDPs, the monad captures a generic notion of uncertainty, while a generic measure function aggregates rewards.

In the present paper we define a notion of correctness for monadic SDPs and identify three conditions that allow us to prove a correctness result for monadic backward induction that is comparable to textbook correctness proofs for ordinary backward induction. The conditions that we impose are fairly general and can be cast in category-theoretical terms using the notion of Eilenberg-Moore-algebra. They hold in familiar settings like those of deterministic or stochastic SDPs but we also give examples in which they fail. Our results show that backward induction can safely be employed for a broader class of SDPs than usually treated in textbooks. However, they also rule out certain instances that were considered admissible in the context of Botta *et al.*'s generic framework.

Our development is formalised in Idris as an extension of the Botta *et al.* framework and the sources are available as supplementary material.

1 Introduction

Backward induction is a method introduced by Bellman (1957) that is routinely used to solve *finite-horizon sequential decision problems (SDP)*. Such problems lie at the core of many applications in economics, logistics, and computer science (Finus *et al.*, 2003; Helm, 2003; Heitzig, 2012; Gintis, 2007; Botta *et al.*, 2013; De Moor, 1995, 1999). Examples

include inventory, scheduling and shortest path problems, but also the search for optimal strategies in games (Bertsekas, 1995; Diederich, 2001).

Botta, Jansson and Ionescu (2017a) propose a generic framework for *monadic* finite-horizon SDPs as generalisation of the deterministic, non-deterministic and stochastic SDPs treated in control theory textbooks (Bertsekas, 1995; Puterman, 2014). This framework allows to specify such problems and to solve them with a generic version of backward induction that we will refer to as *monadic backward induction*.

The Botta-Jansson-Ionescu-framework, subsequently referred to as *BJI-framework*, *BJI-theory* or simply *framework*, already includes a verification of monadic backward induction with respect to a certain underlying *value* function (see Sec. 3.2). However, in the literature on stochastic SDPs this formulation of the function is itself part of the backward induction algorithm and needs to be verified against an optimisation criterion, the *expected total reward* (Puterman, 2014, Ch. 4.2). For stochastic SDPs semi-formal proofs can be found in textbooks – but monadic SDPs are substantially more general than the stochastic SDPs for which these results are established. This observation raises a number of questions:

- What exactly should “correctness” mean for a solution of monadic SDPs?
- Does monadic backward induction provide correct solutions in this sense for monadic SDPs in their full generality?
- And if not, is there a class of monadic SDPs for which monadic backward induction does provide provably correct solutions?

In the present paper we address these questions and make the following contributions to answering them:

- We put forward a formal specification that monadic backward induction should meet in order to be considered “correct” as solution method for monadic SDPs. This specification uses an optimisation criterion that is a generic version of the *expected total reward* of standard control theory textbooks.¹ In analogy, we call this criterion *measured total reward*.
- We consider the value function underlying monadic backward induction as “correct” if it computes the *measured total reward*.
- If the value function is correct, monadic backward induction can be proven to be correct in our sense by extending the result of Botta *et al.* (2017a). However, we show that this is not necessarily the case, i.e. the value function does not compute the *measured total reward* for arbitrary monadic SDPs.
- We therefore formulate conditions that identify a class of monadic SDPs for which the value function and thus monadic backward induction can be shown to be correct. The conditions are fairly simple and allow for a neat description in category-theoretical terms using the notion of Eilenberg-Moore-algebra.
- We give a formalised proof that monadic backward induction fulfils the correctness criterion if the conditions hold. This correctness result can be seen as a generic version of

¹ Note that in control theory backward induction is often referred to as *the dynamic programming algorithm* where the term *dynamic programming* is used in the original sense of Bellman (1957).

correctness results for standard backward induction like (Bertsekas, 1995, Prop. 1.3.1) and (Puterman, 2014, Th. 4.5.1.c).

Our results rule out the application of backward induction to certain monadic SDPs that were previously considered as admissible in the BJI-framework. Thus, they complement the verification result of Botta *et al.* and provide a necessary clarification. Still, the new conditions are simple enough to be checked for non-standard instantiations of the framework. This allows to broaden the applicability of backward induction to settings which are not commonly discussed in the literature and to obtain a formalised proof of correctness with considerably less effort. It is worth stressing that our conditions can be useful for anyone interested in applying monadic backward induction in non-standard situations – completely independent of the BJI-framework.

Finally, the value function underlying monadic backward induction is also interesting in itself. Given the conditions hold, it can be used to compute the measured total reward efficiently, using a method reminiscent of a *thinning* algorithm (Bird & Gibbons, 2020, Ch. 10).

For the reader unfamiliar with SDPs, we provide a brief informal overview and two simple examples in the next section. We recap the BJI-framework and its (partial) verification result for monadic backward induction in Sec. 3. In Sec. 4 we specify correctness for monadic backward induction and the BJI-value function. We also show that in the general monadic case the value function does not necessarily meet the specification. To resolve this problem, we identify conditions under which the value function does meet the specification. These conditions are stated and analysed in Sec. 5. In Sec. 6 we prove that, given the conditions hold, the BJI-value function and monadic backward induction are correct in the sense defined in Sec. 4. We discuss the conditions from a more abstract perspective in Sec. 7 and conclude in Sec. 8.

Throughout the paper we use Idris as our host language (Brady, 2013, 2017). We assume some familiarity with Haskell-like syntax and notions like *functor* and *monad* as used in functional programming. We tacitly consider types as logical statements and programs as proofs, justified by the propositions-as-types correspondence (for an accessible introduction see Wadler, 2015).

Source code. Our development is formalised in Idris as an extension of a lightweight version of the BJI-framework. The proofs are machine-checked and the source code is available as supplementary material attached to this paper. The sources of this document have been written in literal Idris and are available at (Brede & Botta, 2021), together with some example code. All source files can be type checked with Idris 1.3.2.

2 Finite-horizon Sequential Decision Problems

In deterministic, non-deterministic and stochastic finite-horizon SDPs, a decision maker seeks to control the evolution of a (*dynamical*) *system* at a finite number of *decision steps* by selecting certain *controls* in sequence, one after the other. The controls available to the

139 decision maker at a given decision step typically depend on the *state* of the system at that
 140 step.

141 In *deterministic* problems, selecting a control in a state at decision step $t: \mathbb{N}$, deter-
 142 mines a unique next state at decision step $t + 1$ through a given *transition function*. In
 143 *non-deterministic* problems, the transition function yields a whole set of *possible* states at
 144 the next decision step. In *stochastic* problems, the transition function yields a *probability*
 145 *distribution* on states at the next decision step.

146 The notion of *monadic* problem generalises that of deterministic, non-deterministic and
 147 stochastic problem through a transition function that yields an M -structure of next states
 148 where M is a monad. For example, the identity monad can be applied to model deter-
 149 ministic systems. Non-deterministic systems can be represented in terms of transition
 150 functions that return lists (or some other representations of sets) of next states. Stochastic
 151 systems can be represented in terms of probability distribution monads (Giry, 1981; Erwig
 152 & Kollmansberger, 2006; Audebaud & Paulin-Mohring, 2009; Jacobs, 2011). The uncer-
 153 tainty monad, the states, the controls and the next function define what is often called a
 154 *decision process*.

155 The idea of sequential decision problems is that each single decision yields a *reward*
 156 and these rewards add up to a *total reward* over all decision steps. Rewards are often
 157 represented by values of a numeric type, and added up using the canonical addition. If
 158 the transition function and thus the evolution of the system is not deterministic, then the
 159 resulting possible total rewards need to be aggregated to yield a single outcome value.
 160 In stochastic SDPs, evolving the underlying stochastic system leads to a probability dis-
 161 tribution on total rewards which is usually aggregated using the familiar *expected value*
 162 measure. The value thus obtained is called the *expected total reward* (Puterman, 2014,
 163 ch. 4.1.2) and its role is central: It is the quantity that is to be optimised in an SDP.

164 In monadic SDPs, the measure is generic, i.e. it is not fixed in advance but has to be
 165 given as part of the specification of a concrete problem. Therefore we will generalise the
 166 notion of *expected total reward* to a corresponding notion for monadic SDPs that we call
 167 *measured total reward* in analogy (see Sec. 4).

168 *Solving a stochastic SDP* consists in *finding a list of rules for selecting controls that*
 169 *maximises the expected total reward for n decision steps when starting at decision step*
 170 *t* . Similarly, we define that *solving a monadic SDP* consists in *finding a list of rules for*
 171 *selecting controls that maximises the measured total reward*. This means that when starting
 172 from any initial state at decision step t , following the computed list of rules for selecting
 173 controls will result in a value that is maximal as measure of the sum of rewards along all
 174 possible trajectories rooted in that initial state.

175 Equivalently, rewards can instead be considered as *costs* that need to be *minimised*. This
 176 dual perspective is taken e.g. in (Bertsekas, 1995). In the subsequent sections we will fol-
 177 low the terminology of the BJI-framework and (Puterman, 2014) and speak of “rewards”,
 178 but our second example below will illustrate the “cost” perspective.

179 In mathematical theories of optimal control, the rules for selecting controls are called
 180 *policies*. A *policy* for a decision step is simply a function that maps each possible state to
 181 a control. As mentioned above, the controls available in a given state typically depend on
 182 that state, thus policies are dependently typed functions. A list of such policies is called a
 183 *policy sequence*.
 184

Fig. 1: Transition graphs for the example SDPs described in Sec. 2. The edge labels denote pairs *control* | *reward* for the associated transitions. In the first example, state and control spaces are constant over time therefore we have omitted the temporal dimension.

The central idea underlying backward induction is to compute a globally optimal solution of a multi-step SDP incrementally by solving local optimisation problems at each decision step. This is captured by *Bellman's principle*: *Extending an optimal policy sequence with an optimal policy yields again an optimal policy sequence*. However, as we will see in Sec. 4.2, one has to carefully check whether for a given SDP backward induction is indeed applicable.

Two features are crucial for finite-horizon, monadic SDPs to be solvable with the BJI-framework that we study in this paper: (1) the number of decision steps has to be given explicitly as input to the backward induction and (2) at each decision step, the number of possible next states has to be *finite*. While (2) is a necessary condition for backward induction to be computable, (1) is a genuine limitation of the BJI-framework: in many SDPs, for example in a game of tic-tac-toe, the number of decision steps is bounded but not known a priori.

Before we discuss the BJI-framework in the next section, we illustrate the notion of sequential decision problem with two simple examples, one in which the purpose is to maximise rewards and one in which the purpose is to minimise costs. Rewards and costs in these examples are just natural numbers and are summed up with ordinary addition. The first example is a non-deterministic SDP. Although it is somewhat oversimplified, it has the advantage of being tractable for computations by hand while still being sufficient as basis for illustrations in sections 3–5. The second example is a deterministic SDP that stands for the important class of scheduling SDPs. This problem highlights why dependent types are necessary to model state and control spaces accurately. As in these simple examples state and control spaces are finite, the transition functions can be described by directed graphs. These are given in Fig. 1.

Example 1 (*A toy climate problem*). Our first example is a variant of a stochastic climate science SDP studied in (Botta *et al.*, 2018), stripped down to a simple non-deterministic SDP. At every decision step, the world may be in one of two *states*, namely *Good* or *Bad*, and the *controls* determine whether a *Low* or a *High* amount of green house gases is emitted into the atmosphere. If the world is in the *Good* state, choosing *Low* emissions will definitely keep the world in the *Good* state, but the result of choosing high emissions is non-deterministic: either the world may stay in the *Good* or tip to the *Bad* state. Similarly, in the *Bad* state, *High* emissions will definitely keep the world in *Bad*, while with *Low* emissions it might either stay in *Bad* or recover and return to the *Good* state. The transitions just described define a non-deterministic *transition function*. The *rewards* associated with each transition are determined by the respective control and reached state. Now we can formulate an SDP: “Which policy sequence will maximise the worst-case sum of rewards along all possible trajectories when taking n decisions starting at decision step t ?”. In this simple example the question is not hard to answer: always choose *Low* emissions, independent of decision step and state. The *optimal policy sequence* for any n and t would thus consist of n constant *Low* functions. But in a more realistic example the situation will be more involved: every option will have its benefits and drawbacks encoded in a more complicated reward function, uncertainties might come with different probabilities, there might be intermediate states, different combinations of control options etc. For more along these lines we refer the interested reader to (Botta *et al.*, 2018).

Example 2 (*Scheduling*). Scheduling problems serve as canonical examples in control theory textbooks. The one we present here is a slightly modified version of (Bertsekas, 1995, Example 1.1.2).

Think of some machine in a factory that can perform different operations, say A, B, C and D . Each of these operations is supposed to be performed once. The machine can only perform one operation at a time, thus an order has to be fixed in which to perform the operations. Setting the machine up for each operation incurs a specific cost that might vary according to which operation has been performed before. Moreover, operation B can only be performed after operation A has already been completed, and operation D only after operation C . It suffices to fix the order in which the first three operations are to be performed as this uniquely determines which will be the fourth task. The aim is now to choose an order that minimises the total cost of performing the four operations.

This situation can be modelled as follows as a problem with three decision steps: The *states at each step* are the sequences of operations already performed, with the empty sequence at step 0. The *controls at a decision step and in a state* are the operations which have not already been performed at previous steps and which are permitted in that state. For example, at decision step 0, only controls A and C are available because of the above constraint on performing B and D . The *transition* and *cost* functions of the problem are depicted by the graph in Fig. 1b. As the problem is deterministic, picking a control will result in a unique next state and each sequence of policies will result in a unique trajectory. In this setting, solving the SDP reduces to finding a control sequence that *minimises the sum of costs along the single resulting trajectory*. In Fig. 1b this is the sequence $CAB(D)$.

3 The BJI-framework

The BJI-framework is a dependently typed formalisation of optimal control theory for finite-horizon, discrete-time SDPs. It extends mathematical formulations for stochastic SDPs (Bertsekas, 1995; Bertsekas & Shreve, 1996; Puterman, 2014) to the general problem of optimal decision making under *monadic* uncertainty.

For monadic SDPs, the framework provides a generic implementation of backward induction. It has been applied to study the impact of uncertainties on optimal emission policies (Botta *et al.*, 2018) and is currently used to investigate solar radiation management problems under tipping point uncertainty (TiPES, 2019–2023).

In a nutshell, the framework consists of two sets of components: one for the *specification* of an SDP and one for its *solution* with monadic backward induction.

3.1 Problem specification components

In the following we discuss the components necessary to specify a monadic SDP.

The first one is the monad M :

$$M : \text{Type} \rightarrow \text{Type}$$

As discussed in the previous section, M accounts for the uncertainties that affect the decision problem. For our first example, we could for instance define M to be *List*. For the second example it suffices to use $M = \text{Id}$ as the problem is deterministic.

Further, the BJI-framework supports the specification of the *states*, the *controls* and the *transition function* of an SDP through

$$\begin{aligned} X & : (t : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \text{Type} \\ Y & : (t : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow X t \rightarrow \text{Type} \\ \text{next} & : (t : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow (x : X t) \rightarrow Y t x \rightarrow M (X (S t)) \end{aligned}$$

The interpretation is that $X t$ represents the states at decision step t .² In the first example of Sec. 2, there are just two states (*Good* and *Bad*) such that X is a constant family:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{data} \text{ State} & = \text{Good} \mid \text{Bad} \\ X _ & = \text{State} \end{aligned}$$

But in the second example the possible states depend on the decision step t . Taking for example step $t = 2$, we could simply define

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{data} \text{ State2} & = \text{AB} \mid \text{AC} \mid \text{CA} \mid \text{CD} \\ X 2 & = \text{State2} \end{aligned}$$

Alternatively, we could employ type dependency in a more systematic way to express that in Ex. 2 states are admissible sequences of actions

$$\mathbf{data} \text{ Act} = A \mid B \mid C \mid D$$

Recall that actions could require that another action was performed before, no action was to be carried out twice and the problem was limited to 3 steps. These conditions might be captured by a type-valued predicate

² Note that in Idris, S and Z are the familiar constructors of the data type \mathbb{N} .

$AdmissibleState : \{t : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow Vect\ t\ Act \rightarrow Type$

and the type of states might then be expressed as dependent pair of a vector of actions and a proof that it is admissible.

$X\ t = (as : Vect\ t\ Act ** AdmissibleState\ as)$

Similarly, $Y\ t\ x$ represents the controls available at decision step t and in state x and $next\ t\ x\ y$ represents the states that can be obtained by selecting control y in state x at decision step t . In our first example, the available controls remain constant over time (*High* or *Low*) like the states, but for the second example, the type dependency is relevant: e.g. we might define (again at step $t = 2$)

data $CtrlAC = B \mid D$
 $Y\ 2\ AC = CtrlAC$

or more elegantly use dependent pairs to define the type of controls, using the observation that an action is an admissible control for some state represented by a vector of actions, if adding the action to the vector results again in an admissible state :

$AdmissibleControl : \{t : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow Vect\ t\ Act \rightarrow Act \rightarrow Type$
 $AdmissibleControl\ as\ a = AdmissibleState\ (a :: as)$

$Y\ t\ x = (a : Act ** AdmissibleControl\ (fst\ x)\ a)$

Recall from Sec. 2 that the monad, the states, the controls and the next function together define a decision process. In order to fully specify a decision problem, one also has to define the rewards obtained at each decision step and the operation that is used to add up rewards. In the BJI-framework, this is done in terms of

$Val : Type$
 $reward : (t : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow (x : X\ t) \rightarrow Y\ t\ x \rightarrow X\ (S\ t) \rightarrow Val$
 $(\oplus) : Val \rightarrow Val \rightarrow Val$

Here, Val is the type of rewards and $reward\ t\ x\ y\ x'$ is the reward obtained by selecting control y in state x if the next state is x' , an element of the state space at step $t + 1$. Note that for deterministic problems it is unnecessary to parameterise the reward function over the next state as it is unique and can thus be obtained from the current state and control. But for non-deterministic problems it is useful to be able to assign rewards depending on the (uncertain) outcome of a transition.

A few remarks are at place here.

- In many applications, Val is a numerical type and the controls of the SDP represent resources (fuel, water, etc.) that come at a cost. In these cases, the reward function encodes the costs and perhaps also the benefits associated with a decision step. Often, the latter also depends both on the current state x and on the next state x' . The BJI-framework nicely copes with all these situations.
- The operation \oplus determines how rewards are added up. It could be a simple arithmetic operation, but it could also be defined in terms of problem-specific parameters, e.g. discount factors to give more weight to current rewards as compared to future rewards.

- Mapping $\text{reward } t x y$ onto $\text{next } t x y$ (remember that M is a monad and thus a functor) yields a value of type $M \text{ Val}$. These are the *possible* rewards obtained by selecting control y in state x at decision step t . In mathematical theories of optimal control, the implicit assumption often is that Val is equal to \mathbb{R} and that the M -structure is a probability distribution on real numbers which can be evaluated with the *expected value* measure. However, in many practical applications, measuring uncertainty of rewards in terms of the expected value is inadequate (Mercure *et al.*, 2020). The BJI-framework therefore takes a generic approach and allows the specification of SDPs in terms of problem-specific measures.

As just discussed, in SDPs with uncertainty a measure is required to aggregate multiple possible rewards. The BJI-framework supports the specification of the measure by:

$$\text{meas} : M \text{ Val} \rightarrow \text{Val}$$

In our first example we could use the minimum of a list as worst-case measure, while in the second example the measure would just be the identity (as the problem is deterministic).

Before we get to the solution components of the BJI-framework, one more ingredient needs to be specified. In the next section we will formalise a notion of optimality for which it is necessary to be able to compare elements of Val . The framework allows users to compare Val -values in terms of a problem specific comparison operator:

$$(\sqsubseteq) : \text{Val} \rightarrow \text{Val} \rightarrow \text{Type}$$

The operator (\sqsubseteq) is required to define a total preorder on Val . In our two examples, we simply have:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Val} &= \mathbb{N} \\ (\oplus) &= (+) \\ (\sqsubseteq) &= (\leq) \end{aligned}$$

Three more ingredients are necessary to fully specify a monadic SDP, but we defer discussing them to when they come up in the next subsection. For illustration, a formalisation of Ex. 1 can be found in Fig. 2. A formalisation of Ex. 2 is included in the supplementary material.

3.2 Problem solution components

The second set of components of the BJI-framework is an extension of the mathematical theory of optimal control for stochastic sequential decision problems to monadic problems. Here, we provide a summary of the theory. Motivation and full details can be found in (Botta *et al.*, 2017b,a, 2018).

The theory formalises the notions of policy (decision rule) from Sec. 2 as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Policy} &: (t : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \text{Type} \\ \text{Policy } t &= (x : X t) \rightarrow Y t x \end{aligned}$$

Policy sequences are then essentially vectors of policies³.

³ The curly brackets in the types of Nil and $(::)$ indicate that t and n are implicit arguments.

Formalisation of Ex. 1:

We use the monoid and preorder structure on \mathbb{N} , i.e. $Val = \mathbb{N}$, $(\oplus) = (+)$, $zero = 0$, $(\leq) = (\sqsubseteq)$.

$M = List$

Measure:

$minList : List \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$

$minList [] = 0$

$minList (x :: []) = x$

$minList (x :: xs) = x \text{ 'minimum' } xs$

$meas = minList$

States and Controls:

data $States = Good \mid Bad$

data $Controls = High \mid Low$

$X \perp = States$

$Y \perp x = Controls$

Transition function:

$next \perp Good Low = [Good]$

$next \perp Bad High = [Bad]$

$next \perp x \quad _y = [Good, Bad]$

Rewards:

$reward \perp _x Low Good = 3$

$reward \perp _x High Good = 2$

$reward \perp _x Low Bad = 1$

$reward \perp _x High Bad = 0$

Fig. 2: A formalisation of Ex. 1 from Sec. 2 .

data $PolicySeq : (t, n : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow Type$ **where**

$Nil : \{t : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow PolicySeq t Z$

$(::) : \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow Policy t \rightarrow PolicySeq (S t) n \rightarrow PolicySeq t (S n)$

Notice the role of the step (time) index t and of the length index n in the constructors of policy sequences: For a policy sequence to make sense, policies for taking decisions at step t can only be prepended to policy sequences for taking *first* decisions at step $t + 1$ and the operation yields policy sequences for taking *first* decisions at step t . Thus the time index allows to ensure a consistency property of policy sequences by construction. As for plain vectors and lists, prepending a policy to a policy sequence of length n yields a policy sequence of length $n + 1$. Both the time and the length index will be useful below: they allow to express that the backward induction algorithm computes policy sequences starting at a specific time and having a specific length depending on its inputs.

The perhaps most important ingredient of backward induction is a *value function* that incrementally measures and adds up rewards. For a given decision problem, the value function takes two arguments: a policy sequence ps for making n decision steps starting from decision step t and an initial state $x : X t$. It computes the value of taking n decision steps according to the policies ps when starting in x . In the BJI-framework, the value function is defined as

$val : \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow PolicySeq t n \rightarrow X t \rightarrow Val$

$val \{t\} Nil x = zero$

$val \{t\} (p :: ps) x = \mathbf{let} \ y = p \ x \ \mathbf{in}$

$\quad \mathbf{let} \ mx' = next \ t \ x \ y \ \mathbf{in}$

$\quad meas \ (map \ (reward \ t \ x \ y \oplus val \ ps) \ mx')$

Notice that, independently of the initial state x , the value of the empty policy sequence is *zero*. This is a problem-specific reference value

$zero : Val$

that has to be provided as part of a problem specification.⁴ It is one of the specification components that we have not discussed in Sec. 3.1. The value of a policy sequence consisting of a first policy p and of a tail policy sequence ps is defined inductively as the measure of an M -structure of Val -values. These values are obtained by first computing the control y dictated by the policy p in state x and the M -structure of possible next states mx' dictated by the transition function $next$. Then, for all x' in mx' the current reward $reward\ t\ x\ y\ x'$ is added to the aggregated outcome for the tail policy sequence $val\ ps\ x'$. Finally, the result of this functorial mapping is aggregated with the problem-specific measure $meas$ to obtain a result of type Val as outcome for the policy sequence $(p :: ps)$. The function which is mapped onto mx' is just a lifted version of \oplus :

$$\begin{aligned} (\oplus) : \{A : Type\} \rightarrow (f, g : A \rightarrow Val) \rightarrow A \rightarrow Val \\ f \oplus g = \lambda a \Rightarrow f\ a \oplus g\ a \end{aligned}$$

We will come back to the value function of the BJI-theory in Sec. 4 where we will contrast it with a function val' that, for a policy sequence ps and an initial state x , computes the measure of the sum of the rewards along all possible trajectories starting at x under ps (the *measured total reward* that we anticipated in Sec. 2). For the time being, though, we accept the notion of value of a policy sequence as put forward in the BJI-theory and we show how the definition of val can be employed to compute policy sequences that are provably optimal in the sense of

$$\begin{aligned} OptPolicySeq : \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow PolicySeq\ t\ n \rightarrow Type \\ OptPolicySeq\ \{t\}\ \{n\}\ ps = (ps' : PolicySeq\ t\ n) \rightarrow (x : X\ t) \rightarrow val\ ps'\ x \sqsubseteq val\ ps\ x \end{aligned}$$

Notice the universal quantification in this definition: A policy sequence ps is defined to be optimal iff $val\ ps'\ x \sqsubseteq val\ ps\ x$ for any policy sequence ps' and for any state x .

The generic implementation of backward induction in the BJI-framework is an application of *Bellman's principle of optimality* mentioned in Sec. 2. In control theory textbooks, this principle is often referred to as *Bellman's equation*. It can be suitably formulated in terms of the notion of *optimal extension*. We say that a policy $p : Policy\ t$ is an optimal extension of a policy sequence $ps : Policy\ (S\ t)\ n$ if it is the case that the value of $p :: ps$ is at least as good as the value of $p' :: ps$ for any policy p' and for any state $x : X\ t$:

$$\begin{aligned} OptExt : \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow PolicySeq\ (S\ t)\ n \rightarrow Policy\ t \rightarrow Type \\ OptExt\ \{t\}\ ps\ p = (p' : Policy\ t) \rightarrow (x : X\ t) \rightarrow val\ (p' :: ps)\ x \sqsubseteq val\ (p :: ps)\ x \end{aligned}$$

With the notion of optimal extension in place, Bellman's principle can be formulated as

$$\begin{aligned} Bellman : \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow \\ (ps : PolicySeq\ (S\ t)\ n) \rightarrow OptPolicySeq\ ps \rightarrow \\ (p : Policy\ t) \rightarrow OptExt\ ps\ p \rightarrow \\ OptPolicySeq\ (p :: ps) \end{aligned}$$

In words: *extending an optimal policy sequence with an optimal extension (of that policy sequence) yields an optimal policy sequence* or shorter *prefixing with optimal extensions preserves optimality*. Proving Bellman's optimality principle is almost straightforward and relies on \sqsubseteq being reflexive and transitive and two *monotonicity* properties:

⁴ The name might suggest that *zero* is supposed to be a neutral element relative to \oplus . However, this is not required by the framework.

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{plusMonSpec} & : \{v1, v2, v3, v4 : \text{Val}\} \rightarrow v1 \sqsubseteq v2 \rightarrow v3 \sqsubseteq v4 \rightarrow (v1 \oplus v3) \sqsubseteq (v2 \oplus v4) \\
\text{measMonSpec} & : \{A : \text{Type}\} \rightarrow (f, g : A \rightarrow \text{Val}) \rightarrow ((a : A) \rightarrow f a \sqsubseteq g a) \rightarrow \\
& \quad (ma : MA) \rightarrow \text{meas} (\text{map } f \text{ ma}) \sqsubseteq \text{meas} (\text{map } g \text{ ma})
\end{aligned}$$

The second condition is a special case of the measure monotonicity requirement originally formulated by Ionescu (2009) in the context of a theory of vulnerability and monadic dynamical systems. It is a natural property and the expected value measure, the worst (best) case measure and any sound statistical measure fulfil it. Like the reference value *zero* discussed above, *plusMonSpec* and *measMonSpec* are specification components of the BJI-framework that we have not discussed in Sec. 3.1. We provide a proof of *Bellman* in Appendix 5. As one would expect, the proof makes essential use of the recursive definition of the function *val* discussed above. As a consequence, this precise definition of *val* plays a crucial role for the verification of backward induction in (Botta *et al.*, 2017a).

Apart from the increased level of generality, the definition of *val* and *Bellman* are in fact just an Idris formalisation of Bellman's equation as formulated in control theory textbooks. With *Bellman* and provided that we can compute optimal extensions of arbitrary policy sequences

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{optExt} & : \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow \text{PolicySeq } (S t) n \rightarrow \text{Policy } t \\
\text{optExtSpec} & : \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow (ps : \text{PolicySeq } (S t) n) \rightarrow \text{OptExt } ps (\text{optExt } ps)
\end{aligned}$$

it is easy to derive an implementation of monadic backward induction that computes provably optimal policy sequences with respect to *val*: first, notice that the empty policy sequence is optimal:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{nilOptPolicySeq} & : \text{OptPolicySeq } \text{Nil} \\
\text{nilOptPolicySeq } \text{Nil } x & = \text{reflexive lteTP zero}
\end{aligned}$$

This is the base case for constructing optimal policy sequences by backward induction, starting from the empty policy sequence:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{bi} & : (t, n : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \text{PolicySeq } t n \\
\text{bi } t \text{ Z} & = \text{Nil} \\
\text{bi } t (S n) & = \text{let } ps = \text{bi } (S t) n \text{ in } \text{optExt } ps :: ps
\end{aligned}$$

That *bi* computes optimal policy sequences with respect to *val* is then proved by induction on *n*, the input that determines the length of the resulting policy sequence:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{biOptVal} & : (t, n : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \text{OptPolicySeq } (\text{bi } t n) \\
\text{biOptVal } t \text{ Z} & = \text{nilOptPolicySeq} \\
\text{biOptVal } t (S n) & = \text{Bellman } ps \text{ ops } p \text{ oep } \textbf{where} \\
ps & : \text{PolicySeq } (S t) n \quad ; \quad ps = \text{bi } (S t) n \\
ops & : \text{OptPolicySeq } ps \quad ; \quad ops = \text{biOptVal } (S t) n \\
p & : \text{Policy } t \quad ; \quad p = \text{optExt } ps \\
oep & : \text{OptExt } ps p \quad ; \quad oep = \text{optExtSpec } ps
\end{aligned}$$

This is the verification result for *bi* of (Botta *et al.*, 2017a).⁵

⁵ Note that *biOptVal* is called *biLemma* in (Botta *et al.*, 2017a). We chose the new name to emphasise that *bi* computes optimal policy sequences with respect to *val*.

3.3 BJI-framework wrap-up.

The specification and solution components discussed in the last two sections are all we need to formulate precisely the problem of correctness for monadic backward induction in the BJI-framework. This is done in the next section. Before turning to it, two further remarks are necessary:

- The theory proposed in (Botta *et al.*, 2017a) is slightly more general than the one summarised above. Here, policies are just functions from states to controls:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Policy} &: (t : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \text{Type} \\ \text{Policy } t &= (x : X t) \rightarrow Y t x \end{aligned}$$

By contrast, in (Botta *et al.*, 2017a), policies are indexed over a number of decision steps n

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Policy} &: (t, n : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \text{Type} \\ \text{Policy } t Z &= \text{Unit} \\ \text{Policy } t (Sm) &= (x : X t) \rightarrow \text{Reachable } x \rightarrow \text{Viable } (Sm) x \rightarrow \text{GoodCtrl } t x m \end{aligned}$$

and their domain for $n > 0$ is restricted to states that are *reachable* and *viable* for n steps. This allows to cope with states whose control set is empty and with transition functions that return empty M -structures of next states. (For a discussion of reachability and viability see (Botta *et al.*, 2017a, Sec. 3.7 and 3.8).)

This generality, however, comes at a cost: Compare e.g. the proof of Bellman’s principle from the last subsection with the corresponding proof in (Botta *et al.*, 2017a, Appendix B). The impact of the reachability and viability constraints on other parts of the theory is even more severe.

Here, we have decided to trade some generality for better readability and opted for a simplified version of the original theory. Still, for the generic backward induction algorithm we need to make sure that it is possible to define policy sequences of the length required for a specific SDP. This can e.g. be done by postulating controls to be non-empty:

$$\text{notEmpty } Y : (t : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow (x : X t) \rightarrow Y t x$$

We also impose a non-emptiness requirement on the transition function *next* that will be discussed in Sec. 7.

$$\text{nextNotEmpty} : \{t : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow (x : X t) \rightarrow (y : Y t x) \rightarrow \text{NotEmpty } (\text{next } t x y)$$

- In section 3.2, we have not discussed under which conditions one can implement optimal extensions of arbitrary policy sequences. This is an interesting topic that is however orthogonal to the purpose of the current paper. For the same reason we have not addressed the question of how to make *bi* more efficient by tabulation. We briefly discuss the specification and implementation of optimal extensions in the BJI-framework in Appendix 7. We refer the reader interested in tabulation of *bi* to [SequentialDecisionProblems.TabBackwardsInduction](#) of (Botta, 2016–2021).

4 Correctness for monadic backward induction

In this section we formally specify the notions of correctness for monadic backward induction bi and the value function val of the BJI-framework that we will study in the remainder of this paper. We develop these notions as generic variants of the corresponding notions for stochastic SDPs.

4.1 Extension of the BJI-framework

In the previous section, we have seen that a monadic SDP can be specified in terms of nine components: M , X , Y , $next$, Val , $zero$, \oplus , \sqsubseteq and $reward$.

Given a policy sequence (optimal or not) and an initial state for an SDP, we can compute the M -structure of possible trajectories starting at that state:

```

data StateCtrlSeq : (t, n : ℕ) → Type where
  Last : {t : ℕ} → X t → StateCtrlSeq t (S Z)
  (##) : {t, n : ℕ} → (x : X t ** Y t x) → StateCtrlSeq (S t) (S n) → StateCtrlSeq (S (S n))

  trj : {t, n : ℕ} → PolicySeq t n → X t → M (StateCtrlSeq t (S n))
  trj {t} Nil x      = pure (Last x)
  trj {t} (p :: ps) x = let y = p x in
    let mx' = next t x y in
      map ((x ** y)##) (mx' >>= trj ps)

```

where we use $StateCtrlSeq$ as type of trajectories. Essentially it is a non-empty list of (dependent) state/control pairs, with the exception of the base case which is a singleton just containing the last state reached.

Furthermore, we can compute the *total reward* for a single trajectory, i.e. its sum of rewards:

```

sumR : {t, n : ℕ} → StateCtrlSeq t n → Val
sumR {t} (Last x)      = zero
sumR {t} ((x ** y) ## xys) = reward t x y (head xys) ⊕ sumR xys

```

where $head$ is the helper function

```

head : {t, n : ℕ} → StateCtrlSeq t (S n) → X t
head (Last x)      = x
head ((x ** y) ## xys) = x

```

By mapping $sumR$ onto an M -structure of trajectories, we obtain an M -structure containing the individual sums of rewards of the trajectories. Now, using the measure function, we can compute the generic analogue of the expected total reward for a policy sequence ps and an initial state x :

```

val' : {t, n : ℕ} → (ps : PolicySeq t n) → (x : X t) → Val
val' ps = meas ∘ map sumR ∘ trj ps

```

As anticipated in Sec. 2 we call the value computed by val' the *measured total reward*. Recall that solving a stochastic SDP commonly means finding a policy sequence that maximises the *expected total reward*. By analogy, we define that solving a monadic SDP means to find a policy sequence that maximises the *measured total reward*. I.e. given t and n , the

645 solution of a monadic SDP is a sequence of n policies that maximises the measure of the
 646 sum of rewards along all possible trajectories of length n that are rooted in an initial state
 647 at step t .

648 Again by analogy to the stochastic case, we define monadic backward induction to be
 649 correct if, for a given SDP, the policy sequence computed by bi is the solution to the SDP.
 650 I.e., we consider bi to be correct if it meets the specification

$$651 \quad biOptMeasTotalReward : (t, n : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow GenOptPolicySeq\ val' (bi\ t\ n)$$

652 where $GenOptPolicySeq$ is a generalised version of the optimality predicate $OptPolicySeq$
 653 from Sec. 3.2. It now takes as an additional parameter the function with respect to which
 654 the policy sequence is to be optimal:

$$655 \quad GenOptPolicySeq : \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow (PolicySeq\ t\ n \rightarrow Xt \rightarrow Val) \rightarrow PolicySeq\ t\ n \rightarrow Type$$

$$656 \quad GenOptPolicySeq\ \{t\}\ \{n\}\ f\ ps = (ps' : PolicySeq\ t\ n) \rightarrow (x : Xt) \rightarrow f\ ps'\ x \sqsubseteq f\ ps\ x$$

658 As recapitulated in Sec. 3.2, Botta *et al.* have already shown that if M is a monad, \sqsubseteq
 659 a total preorder and \oplus and $meas$ fulfil two monotonicity conditions, then $bi\ t\ n$ yields
 660 an optimal policy sequence with respect to the value function val in the sense that
 661 $val\ ps'\ x \sqsubseteq val\ (bi\ t\ n)\ x$ for any policy sequence ps' and initial state x , for arbitrary $t, n : \mathbb{N}$.
 662 Or, expressed using the generalised optimality predicate, that the type

$$663 \quad GenOptPolicySeq\ \{t\}\ \{n\}\ val\ (bi\ t\ n)$$

664 is inhabited. As seen in Sec. 3.2, the function val measures and adds rewards incrementally.
 665 But does it always compute the measured total reward like val' ? Modulo differences in the
 666 presentation Puterman (2014, Theorem 4.2.1) suggests that for standard stochastic SDPs,
 667 val and val' are extensionally equal, which in turn allows the use of backward induction
 668 for solving these SDPs. Generalising, we therefore consider val as correct if it fulfils the
 669 specification

$$671 \quad valMeasTotalReward : \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow (ps : PolicySeq\ t\ n) \rightarrow (x : Xt) \rightarrow val\ ps\ x = val'\ ps\ x$$

672 If this equality held for the general monadic SDPs of the BJI-theory, we could prove
 673 the correctness of bi as immediate corollary of $valMeasTotalReward$ and Botta *et al.*'s
 674 result $biOptVal$. The statement $biOptMeasTotalReward$ can be seen as a generic version of
 675 textbook correctness statements for backward induction as solution method for stochastic
 676 SDPs like (Bertsekas, 1995, prop.1.3.1) or (Puterman, 2014, Theorem 4.5.1.c). By proving
 677 $valMeasTotalReward$ we could therefore extend the verification of (Botta *et al.*, 2017a)
 678 and obtain a stronger correctness result for monadic backward induction.

680 Our main objective in the remainder of the paper is therefore to prove that
 681 $valMeasTotalReward$ holds. But there is a problem.

683 4.2 The problem with the BJI-value function

684 A closer look at val and val' reveals two quite different computational patterns: applied to
 685 a policy sequence ps of length $n + 1$ and a state x , the function val directly evaluates $meas$
 686 on the M -structure of rewards corresponding to the possible next states after one step.
 687 This entails further evaluations of $meas$ for each possible next state. By contrast, $val'\ ps\ x$
 688

entails only one evaluation of *meas*, independently of the length of *ps*. The computation, however, builds up an intermediate *M*-structure of state-control sequences. The elements of this *M*-structure, the state-control sequences, are then consumed by *sumR* and finally the *M*-structure of rewards is reduced by *meas*.

For illustration, let us revisit Ex. 1 from Sec. 2 as formalised in Fig. 2. To do an example calculation with *val* and *val'* we first need a concrete policy sequence as input. The simplest two policies are the two constant policies:

```

697     constH : (t : ℕ) → Policy t
698     constH ⊣ = const High
699     constL : (t : ℕ) → Policy t
700     constL ⊣ = const Low
701

```

From these, we can define a policy sequence

```

703     ps : PolicySeq 0 3
704     ps = constH 0 :: (constL 1 :: (constH 2 :: Nil))
705

```

It is instructive to compute *val ps Good* and *val' ps Good* by hand. Recall that in this example, we have *M* = *List* with ($\gg\equiv$) = *concatMap* and *Val* = \mathbb{N} with $\oplus = +$. The measure *meas* thus needs to have the type *List* $\mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$. Without instantiating *meas* for the moment, the computations roughly exhibit the structure

```

710     val ps Good = meas [2 + meas [3 + meas [2, 0]], 0 + meas [3 + meas [2, 0], 1 + meas [0]]]
711     val' ps Good = meas [7, 5, 5, 3, 1]
712

```

and it is not “obviously clear” that *val* and *val'* are extensionally equal without further knowledge about *meas*.

In the deterministic case, i.e. for *M* = *Id* and *meas* = *id*, *val ps x* and *val' ps x* are indeed equal for all *ps* and *x*, without imposing any further conditions (as we will see in Sec. 6). For the stochastic case, (Puterman, 2014, Theorem 4.2.1) suggests that the equality should hold. But for the monadic case, no such result has been established. And as it turns out, in general the functions *val* and *val'* are not unconditionally equal – consider the following counter-example: We continue in the setting of Ex. 1 from above, but now instantiate the measure to the plain arithmetic sum

```

721     meas = foldr (+) 0
722

```

This measure fulfils the monotonicity condition (*measMonSpec*, Sec. 3.2) imposed by the BJI-framework. But if we instantiate the above computations with it, then we get *val ps Good* = 13 and *val' ps Good* = 21! We thus see that the equality between *val* and *val'* cannot hold unconditionally in the generic setting of the BJI-framework. In the next section we therefore present conditions under which the equality *does* hold.

5 Correctness conditions

We now formulate three conditions on combinations of the monad, the measure function and the binary operation \oplus that imply the extensional equality of *val* and *val'*:

Condition 1. The measure needs to be left-inverse to *pure*:⁶

$$\text{measPureSpec} : \text{meas} \circ \text{pure} \doteq \text{id}$$

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \text{Val} & & \\ \text{pure} \downarrow & \searrow \text{id} & \\ \text{MVal} & \xrightarrow{\text{meas}} & \text{Val} \end{array}$$

Condition 2. Applying the measure after *join* needs to be extensionally equal to applying it after *map meas*:

$$\text{measJoinSpec} : \text{meas} \circ \text{join} \doteq \text{meas} \circ \text{map meas}$$

$$\begin{array}{ccc} M(\text{MVal}) & \xrightarrow{\text{map meas}} & \text{MVal} \\ \text{join} \downarrow & & \downarrow \text{meas} \\ \text{MVal} & \xrightarrow{\text{meas}} & \text{Val} \end{array}$$

Condition 3. For arbitrary $v : \text{Val}$ and non-empty $mv : \text{MVal}$ applying the measure after mapping $(v \oplus)$ onto mv needs to be equal to applying $(v \oplus)$ after the measure:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{measPlusSpec} : (v : \text{Val}) \rightarrow (mv : \text{MVal}) \rightarrow (\text{NotEmpty } mv) \rightarrow \\ (\text{meas} \circ \text{map } (v \oplus)) \text{ } mv = ((v \oplus) \circ \text{meas}) \text{ } mv \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \text{MVal} & \xrightarrow{\text{map}(v \oplus)} & \text{MVal} \\ \text{meas} \downarrow & & \downarrow \text{meas} \\ \text{Val} & \xrightarrow{(v \oplus)} & \text{Val} \end{array}$$

Essentially, these conditions assure that the measure is well-behaved relative to the monad structure and the \oplus -operation. They arise by, again, generalising from the standard example of stochastic SDPs with a probability monad, the *expected value* as measure and ordinary addition as \oplus . The first two conditions are lifting properties that allow to do computations either in the monad or the underlying structure with the same result. The third condition is a distributivity law. For the computation of the measured total reward it means that instead of adding the current reward to the outcome of each trajectory and then measuring, one may as well first measure the outcomes and then add the current reward.

⁶ The symbol \doteq denotes *extensional* equality, see Appendix 1.2

To illustrate the conditions, let us consider a simple representation of discrete probability distributions like in (Erwig & Kollmansberger, 2006).

$Dist : Type \rightarrow Type$
 $Dist\ Omega = List\ (Omega, Double)$

with

$distMap : \{A, B : Type\} \rightarrow (f : A \rightarrow B) \rightarrow Dist\ A \rightarrow Dist\ B$
 $distMap\ f\ aps = [(f\ (fst\ ap),\ snd\ ap) \mid ap \leftarrow aps]$

$distPure : \{A : Type\} \rightarrow A \rightarrow Dist\ A$
 $distPure\ a = [(a, 1.0)]$

$distJoin : \{A : Type\} \rightarrow (Dist\ (Dist\ A)) \rightarrow Dist\ A$
 $distJoin\ apsp = concat\ [[(fst\ ap, snd\ ap * snd\ ap) \mid ap \leftarrow fst\ ap] \mid apsp \leftarrow apsp]$

$Val = Double$ and as measure the expected value

$expected : Dist\ Double \rightarrow Double$
 $expected\ dps = sum\ [fst\ dp * snd\ dp \mid dp \leftarrow dps]$

With $meas = expected$ and $\oplus = +$, we can now consider the three conditions from above.

Condition 1. The first condition $measPureSpec$ holds since 1.0 is neutral for $*$.

$expected \circ distPure\ a = a * 1.0 = a$

The second and the third condition require some arithmetic reasoning, so let us just consider them for two examples. Let a, b, c, d be variables of type $Double$ and say we have distributions

$dps1 : Dist\ Double$
 $dps1 = [(a, 0.5), (b, 0.3), (c, 0.2)]$

$dps2 : Dist\ Double$
 $dps2 = [(a, 0.4), (d, 0.6)]$

$dpdps : Dist\ (Dist\ Double)$
 $dpdps = [(dps1, 0.1), (dps2, 0.9)]$

Condition 2. Then the second condition $measJoinSpec$ instantiates to

$(expected \circ distJoin)\ dpdps = (expected \circ distMap\ expected)\ dpdps$

This equality holds because of the standard properties of addition and multiplication:

$(expected \circ distJoin)\ dpdps =$
 $expected\ [(a, 0.5 * 0.1), (b, 0.3 * 0.1), (c, 0.2 * 0.1), (a, 0.4 * 0.9), (d, 0.6 * 0.9)] =$
 $(a * 0.5 * 0.1) + (b * 0.3 * 0.1) + (c * 0.2 * 0.1) + (a * 0.4 * 0.9) + (d * 0.6 * 0.9) =$
 $((a * 0.5 + b * 0.3 + c * 0.2) * 0.1 + (a * 0.4 + d * 0.6) * 0.9 =$
 $expected\ [(a * 0.5 + b * 0.3 + c * 0.2, 0.1), (a * 0.4 + d * 0.6, 0.9)] =$
 $(expected \circ distMap\ expected)\ dpdps$

Condition 3. For the third condition *measPlusSpec*, consider for some $v : \text{Double}$ the equation

$$(\text{expected} \circ \text{distMap } (v+)) \text{ dps1} = ((v+) \circ \text{expected}) \text{ dps1}$$

Again using the usual arithmetic laws for $+$ and $*$, we can calculate

$$\begin{aligned} \text{expected } (\text{distMap } (v+) [(a, 0.5), (b, 0.3), (c, 0.2)]) &= \\ (v + a) * 0.5 + (v + b) * 0.3 + (v + c) * 0.2 &= \\ (v * 0.5 + a * 0.5) + (v * 0.3 + b * 0.3) + (v * 0.2 + c * 0.2) &= \\ (v * 0.5 + v * 0.3 + v * 0.2) + (a * 0.5 + b * 0.3 + c * 0.2) &= \\ v + \text{expected } [(a, 0.5), (b, 0.3), (c, 0.2)] \end{aligned}$$

As we can see, an essential ingredient for the equality to hold is that the mapped occurrences of $(v+)$ are weighted by the probabilities which add up to 1.

Note that in this example, we have glossed over problems that might arise from the use of *Dist* to represent probability distributions.⁷ We will briefly address probability monads and the expected value from a more abstract perspective in Subsection 5.2.

5.1 Examples and counter-examples

Besides the motivating example above, let us now consider some more functions that have the correct type to serve as a measure, and that do or do not fulfil the three conditions.

Simple examples of admissible measures are the minimum (*minList* as defined in Fig. 2) or maximum (*maxList* = *foldr* ‘maximum’ 0) of a list for $M = \text{List}$ with \mathbb{N} as type of values and ordinary addition as \oplus . It is straightforward to prove that the conditions hold for these two measures and the proofs for *maxList* are included in the supplementary material.

The function *length* is a very simple counter-example: It has the right type for a list measure but fails all three of the conditions. As to other counter-examples, let us revisit the conditions one by one. Throughout, we use $M = \text{List}$ with *map* = *listMap*, *join* = *concat* and $\oplus = +$ (the canonical addition for the respective type of *Val*).

Condition 1. We remain in the setting of Ex. 1 with $\text{Val} = \mathbb{N}$, and just vary the measure. Using a somewhat contrived variation of *maxList*

$$\begin{aligned} \text{maxListVar} &: \text{List } \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N} \\ \text{maxListVar} &= \text{foldr } (\lambda x, v \Rightarrow (x + 1 \text{ ‘maximum’ } v)) 0 \end{aligned}$$

with *meas* = *maxListVar* it suffices to consider that for an arbitrary $n : \mathbb{N}$

$$(\text{maxListVar} \circ \text{pure}) n = \text{maxListVar } [n] = (n + 1) \text{ ‘maximum’ } 0 = n + 1 \neq n = \text{id } n$$

to see that now the condition *measPureSpec* fails.

Condition 2. To exhibit a measure that fails the condition *measJoinSpec*, we switch to $\text{Val} = \text{Double}$ and use the arithmetic average

⁷ For the sake of simplicity, we do not address (important) conceptual questions concerning the representation of probability distributions or the problems caused by the use of floating point arithmetic in this example. Note however, that the chosen type *Prob* does e.g. neither enforce that the probabilities lie in the interval $[0, 1]$ nor that they add up to 1. These properties would however be crucial for actual proofs.

875 $avg : List\ Double \rightarrow Double$
 876 $avg [] = 0.0$
 $avg\ ds = sum\ ds / cast\ (length\ ds)$

877 as measure $meas = avg$. Taking a list of lists of different lengths like $[[1], [2, 3]]$ we have

878 $avg\ (concat\ [[1], [2, 3]]) = avg\ [1, 2, 3] = 2$
 879 \neq
 880 $avg\ (listMap\ avg\ [[1], [2, 3]]) = avg\ [1, 2.5] = 1.75$
 881

882
 883 **Condition 3.** Let again $Val = \mathbb{N}$ to take another look at our counter-example from the
 884 last section with $meas = sum$, the arithmetic sum of a list. It does fulfil $measPureSpec$ and
 885 $measJoinSpec$, the first by definition, the second by structural induction using the associa-
 886 tivity of $+$. But it fails to fulfil $measPlusSpec$. If the list has the form $a :: as$, we would have
 887 to show the following equality for $measPlusSpec$ to hold:

888 $(sum \circ listMap\ (v+))\ (a :: as) = ((v+) \circ sum)\ (a :: as)$
 889

890 Clearly, if $v \neq 0$ and $as \neq []$ this equality cannot hold. This is why in the last section the
 891 equality of val and val' failed for $meas = sum$.

892 A similar failure would arise if we chose $meas = foldr\ (*)\ 1$ instead, as $+$ does not dis-
 893 tribute over $*$. But if we turned the situation around by setting $\oplus = *$ and $meas = sum$, the
 894 condition $measPlusSpec$ would hold thanks to the usual arithmetic distributivity law for $*$
 895 over $+$.

896 All of the measures considered in this subsection do fulfil the $measMonSpec$ condition
 897 imposed by the BJI-theory. This raises the question how previously admissible measures
 898 are impacted by adding the three new conditions to the framework.
 899

900 5.2 Impact on previously admissible measures

901 As we have seen in Sec. 3.2, the BJI-framework already requires measures to fulfil the
 902 monotonicity condition
 903

904 $measMonSpec : \{A : Type\} \rightarrow (f, g : A \rightarrow Val) \rightarrow ((a : A) \rightarrow (f\ a) \sqsubseteq (g\ a)) \rightarrow$
 905 $(ma : M\ A) \rightarrow meas\ (map\ f\ ma) \sqsubseteq meas\ (map\ g\ ma)$
 906

907 Botta *et al.* show that the arithmetic average (for $M = List$), the worst-case measure (for
 908 $M = List$ and for a probability monad $M = Prob$) and the expected value measure (for
 909 $M = Prob$) all fulfil $measMonSpec$. Thus, a natural question is whether these measures
 910 also fulfil the three additional requirements.
 911

912 **Expected value for probability distributions.** As already discussed, most applications
 913 of backward induction concern stochastic SDPs where possible rewards are aggregated
 914 using the expected value measure from probability theory, commonly denoted as E .

915 Essentially, for a numerical type Q , the expected value of a probability distribution on Q
 916 is

917 $E : Num\ Q \Rightarrow Prob\ Q \rightarrow Q$
 918 $E\ pq = sum\ [q * prob\ pq\ q \mid q \leftarrow supp\ pq]$
 919

where $prob$ and $supp$ are generic functions that encode the notions of *probability* and of *support* associated with a finite probability distribution:

$$prob : \{A : Type\} \rightarrow Prob A \rightarrow A \rightarrow Q$$

$$supp : \{A : Type\} \rightarrow Prob A \rightarrow List A$$

For pa and a of suitable types, $prob pa a$ represents the probability of a according to pa . Similarly, $supp pa$ returns a list of those values whose probability is not zero in pa . The probability function $prob$ has to fulfil the axioms of probability theory. In particular,

$$sum [prob pa a \mid a \leftarrow supp pa] = 1$$

This condition implies that probability distributions cannot be empty, a precondition of *measPlusSpec*. Putting forward minimal specifications for $prob$ and $supp$ is not completely trivial but if the $+$ -operation associated with Q is commutative and associative, if $*$ distributes over $+$ and if the map and $join$ associated with $Prob$ – for f, a, b, pa and ppa of suitable types – fulfil the conservation law

$$prob (map f pa) b = sum [prob pa a \mid a \leftarrow supp pa, f a == b]$$

and the total probability law

$$prob (join ppa) a = sum [prob pa a * prob ppa pa \mid pa \leftarrow supp ppa]$$

then the expected value fulfils *measPureSpec*, *measJoinSpec* and *measPlusSpec*. This is not surprising since – as stated above – this has been the guiding example for the generalisation to monadic SDPs and the formulation of the three conditions.

Average and arithmetic sum. As can already be concluded from the corresponding counter-examples in the previous subsection, neither the plain arithmetic average nor the arithmetic sum are suited as measure when using the standard monad structure on *List* to represent non-deterministic uncertainty. We think this is an important observation, as the average seems innocent enough to come to mind as a simple way to represent uniformly distributed outcomes: “*The probability of each element can simply be inferred from the length of the list – so why bother to explicitly deal with probabilities?*” Although our counter-example shows that this idea is flawed, the intuition behind it can be employed to define an alternative, but less general monad structure on lists by incorporating the averaging operation into the joining of lists (i.e. by choosing $join = map avg$). However, this only makes sense for types that are instances of the *Num* and *Fractional* type classes, and naturality only holds for a restricted class of functions (namely additive functions). As a consequence, this alternative structure does not seem particularly useful for our current purpose either.

Worst-case measures. In many important applications in climate impact research but also in portfolio management and sports, decisions are taken as to minimise the consequences of worst case outcomes. Depending on how “worse” is defined, the corresponding measures might pick the maximum or minimum from an M -structure of values. In the previous subsection we considered an example in which the monad was *List*, the operation \oplus plain addition together with either *maxList* or *minList* as measure. And indeed we can prove that for both measures the three requirements hold (the proofs for *maxList* can be found

in the supplementary material). This gives us a useful notion of worst-case measure that is admissible for monadic backward induction.

We can thus conclude that the new requirements hold for certain familiar measures, but that they also rule out certain instances that were considered admissible in the BJI-framework. Given the three conditions *measPureSpec*, *measJoinSpec*, *measPlusSpec* hold, we can prove the extensional equality of the functions *val* and *val'* generically. This is what we will do in the next section.

6 Correctness Proofs

In this section we show that *val* (Sec. 3.2) and *val'* (Sec. 4) are extensionally equal

$$valMeasTotalReward : \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow (ps : PolicySeq\ t\ n) \rightarrow (x : X\ t) \rightarrow val'\ ps\ x = val\ ps\ x$$

given the three conditions from the previous section hold. As a corollary we then obtain our correctness result for monadic backward induction.

We can understand the proof of *valMeasTotalReward* as an optimising program transformation from the less efficient but “obviously correct” implementation *val'* to the more efficient implementation *val*. Therefore the equational reasoning proofs in this section will proceed from *val'* to *val*. In Sec. 5 we have stated sufficient conditions for this transformation to be possible: *measPureSpec*, *measJoinSpec*, *measPlusSpec*. We also have seen the different computational patterns that the two implementations exhibit: While *val'* first computes all possible trajectories for the given policy sequence and initial state, then computes their individual sum of rewards and finally applies the measure once, *val* computes its final result by adding the current reward to an intermediate outcome and applying the measure locally at each decision step. This suggests that a transformation from *val'* to *val* will essentially have to push the application of the measure into the recursive computation of the sum of rewards. The proof will be carried out by induction on the structure of policy sequences.

6.1 Deterministic Case

To get a first intuition, let's have a look at what the induction step looks like in the deterministic case (i.e. if we fix monad and measure to be identities):

$$\begin{aligned} valMeasTotalReward\ (p :: ps)\ x &= \\ (val'\ (p :: ps)\ x) &= \{ \text{by definition of } val' \} = \\ (sumR\ ((x ** y) \#\# trj\ ps\ x')) &= \{ \text{by definition of } sumR \} = \\ (r\ (head\ (trj\ ps\ x')) \oplus val'\ ps\ x') &= \{ \text{by } headLemma \} = \\ (r\ x' \oplus val'\ ps\ x') &= \{ \text{by induction hypothesis} \} = \\ (r\ x' \oplus val\ ps\ x') &= \{ \text{by definition of } val \} = \\ (val\ (p :: ps)\ x) & \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

where $y = p x$, $x' = \text{next } t x y$ and $r = \text{reward } t x y$. In the proof sketch, we have first applied the definitions of val' and sumR . Using the fact that in the deterministic case trj returns exactly one state-control sequence and that the *head* of any trajectory starting in x' is just x' (let us call the latter *headLemma*), the left-hand side of the sum simplifies to $r x'$. Its right-hand side amounts to $\text{val}' p s x'$ so that we can apply the induction hypothesis. The rest of the proof only relies on definitional equalities. Thus in the deterministic case val and val' are unconditionally extensionally equal – or rather, the conditions of Sec. 5 are trivially fulfilled.

6.2 Lemmas

To prove the general, monadic case, we proceed similarly. This time, however, the situation is complicated by the presence of the abstract monad M . Instead of being able to use the type structure of some concrete monad, we need to leverage on the properties of M , meas and \oplus postulated in Sec. 5. To facilitate the main proof, we first prove three lemmas about the interaction of the measure with the monad structure and the \oplus -operator on Val . Machine-checked proofs are given in the Appendices 2, 3 and 4. The monad laws we use are stated in Appendix 1.2. In the remainder of this section, we discuss semi-formal versions of the proofs.

Monad algebras. The first lemma allows us to lift and eliminate an application of the monad's *join* operation:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{measAlgLemma} : \{A, B : \text{Type}\} \rightarrow (f : B \rightarrow \text{Val}) \rightarrow (g : A \rightarrow M B) \rightarrow \\ (\text{meas} \circ \text{map} (\text{meas} \circ \text{map } f \circ g)) \doteq (\text{meas} \circ \text{map } f \circ \text{join} \circ \text{map } g) \end{aligned}$$

The proof of this lemma hinges on the condition measJoinSpec . It allows to trade the application of *join* against an application of $\text{map } \text{meas}$. The rest is just standard reasoning with monad and functor laws, i.e. we use that the functorial map for M preserves composition and that *join* is a natural transformation:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{measAlgLemma } f g m a = \\ ((\text{meas} \circ \text{map} (\text{meas} \circ \text{map } f \circ g)) m a) & \quad =\{\text{map preserves composition}\} = \\ ((\text{meas} \circ \text{map} (\text{meas} \circ \text{map } f) \circ \text{map } g) m a) & \quad =\{\text{map preserves composition}\} = \\ ((\text{meas} \circ \text{map } \text{meas} \circ \text{map} (\text{map } f) \circ \text{map } g) m a) & \quad =\{\text{by } \text{measJoinSpec}\} = \\ ((\text{meas} \circ \text{join} \circ \text{map} (\text{map } f) \circ \text{map } g) m a) & \quad =\{\text{join is a natural transformation}\} = \\ ((\text{meas} \circ \text{map } f \circ \text{join} \circ \text{map } g) m a) & \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

This lemma is generic in the sense that it holds for arbitrary Eilenberg-Moore algebras of a monad. Here we prove it for the framework's measure meas , but note that in the appendix we prove a generic version that is then appropriately instantiated.

Head/trajectory interaction. The second lemma amounts to a lifted version of *headLemma* in the deterministic case. Mapping *head* onto an M -structure of trajectories computed with trj results in an M -structure filled with the initial states of these trajectories; similarly, mapping $(r \circ \text{head} \oplus s)$ onto $\text{trj } p s x$ for functions r and s of appropriate

type is the same as mapping $(const(r.x) \oplus s)$ onto $trjps\ x$ (where $const$ is the constant function). We can prove

$$\begin{aligned} headTrjLemma : \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow (ps : PolicySeq\ t\ n) \rightarrow (r : Xt \rightarrow Val) \rightarrow \\ (s : StateCtrlSeq\ t\ (S\ n) \rightarrow Val) \rightarrow (x : Xt) \rightarrow \\ (map\ (r \circ head \oplus s) \circ trjps)\ x = \\ (map\ (const\ (r.x) \oplus s) \circ trjps)\ x \end{aligned}$$

by doing a case split on ps . In case $ps = Nil$, the equality holds because the monad's $pure$ is a natural transformation and in case $ps = p :: ps'$ because M 's functorial map preserves composition.

Measure/sum interaction. The third lemma allows us to both commute the measure into the right summand of an \oplus -sum and to perform the head/trajectory simplification. It lies at the core of the relationship between val and val' .

$$\begin{aligned} measSumLemma : \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow (ps : PolicySeq\ t\ n) \rightarrow \\ (r : Xt \rightarrow Val) \rightarrow \\ (s : StateCtrlSeq\ t\ (S\ n) \rightarrow Val) \rightarrow \\ (meas \circ map\ (r \circ head \oplus s) \circ trjps) \doteq \\ (r \oplus meas \circ map\ s \circ trjps) \end{aligned}$$

Recall that our third condition from Sec. 5, $measPlusSpec$, plays the role of a distributive law and allows us to “factor out” a partially applied sum $(v \oplus)$ for arbitrary $v : Val$. Given that $measPlusSpec$ holds, the lemma is provable by simple equational reasoning using the above head-trajectory lemma and the fact that map preserves composition:

$$\begin{aligned} measSumLemma\ ps\ r\ s\ x' = \\ ((meas \circ map\ (r \circ head \oplus s) \circ trjps)\ x') &= \{ \text{by } headTrjLemma \} = \\ ((meas \circ map\ (const\ (r.x') \oplus s) \circ trjps)\ x') &= \{ \text{by definition of } \oplus, \circ \} = \\ ((meas \circ map\ ((const\ (r.x') \oplus id) \circ s) \circ trjps)\ x') &= \{ \text{map preserves composition} \} = \\ ((meas \circ map\ (const\ (r.x') \oplus id) \circ map\ s \circ trjps)\ x') &= \{ \text{by definition of } \oplus \} = \\ ((meas \circ map\ ((r.x') \oplus) \circ map\ s \circ trjps)\ x') &= \{ \text{by } measPlusSpec \} = \\ (((r.x') \oplus) \circ meas \circ map\ s \circ trjps)\ x') &= \{ \text{by definition of } \oplus \} = \\ ((r \oplus meas \circ map\ s \circ trjps)\ x') & \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

Notice how $measPlusSpec$ is used to transform an application of $meas \circ map\ ((r.x') \oplus)$ into an application of $((r.x') \oplus) \circ meas$. This is essential to simplify the computation of the measured total reward: instead of first adding the current reward to the intermediate outcome of each individual trajectory and then measuring the outcomes, one can first measure the intermediate outcomes of the trajectories and then add the current reward.

6.3 Correctness of the BJI-value function

With the above lemmas in place, we now prove that val is extensionally equal to val' .

Let $t, n : \mathbb{N}$, $ps : PolicySeq\ t\ n$. We prove $valMeasTotalReward$ by induction on ps .

Base case. We need to show that for all $x : X t$, $val' Nil x = val Nil x$. The right hand side of this equation reduces to *zero* by definition. The left hand side can be simplified to *meas (pure zero)* since *pure* is a natural transformation. At this point, our first condition, *measPureSpec*, comes into play: Using that *meas* is inverse to *pure* on the left, we can conclude that the equality holds.

In equational reasoning style: For all $x : X t$,

$$\begin{aligned}
valMeasTotalReward Nil x &= \\
&(val' Nil x) && \quad =\{\text{by definition of } val'\} = \\
&(meas (map sumR (trj Nil x))) && \quad =\{\text{by definition of } trj\} = \\
&(meas (map sumR (pure (Last x)))) && \quad =\{\text{pure is a natural transformation}\} = \\
&(meas (pure (sumR (Last x)))) && \quad =\{\text{by definition of } sumR\} = \\
&(meas (pure zero)) && \quad =\{\text{by } measPureSpec\} = \\
&(zero) && \quad =\{\text{by definition of } val\} = \\
&(val Nil x)
\end{aligned}$$

Step case. The induction hypothesis (*IH*) is: for all $x : X t$, $val' ps x = val ps x$. We have to show that *IH* implies that for all $p : Policy t$ and $x : X t$, the equality $val' (p :: ps) x = val (p :: ps) x$ holds.

For brevity (and to economise on brackets), let in the following $y = p x$, $mx' = next t x y$, $r = reward t x y$, $trjps = trj ps$, and $consxy = ((x ** y)##)$.

As in the base case, all that has to be done on the *val*-side of the equation only depends on definitional equality. However it is more involved to bring the *val'*-side into a form in which the induction hypothesis can be applied. This is where we leverage on the lemmas proved above.

By definition and because *map* preserves composition, we know that $val' (p :: ps) x$ is equal to $(meas \circ map ((r \circ head) \oplus sumR)) (mx' \gg\gg trjps)$. We use the relation between the monad's *bind* and *join* to eliminate the *bind*-operator from the term. Now we can apply the first lemma from above, *measAlgLemma*, to lift and eliminate the *join* operation.

To commute the measure under the \oplus and get rid of the application of *head*, we use our third lemma, *measSumLemma*. At this point we can apply the induction hypothesis and the resulting term is equal to $val ps x$ by definition.

The more detailed equational reasoning proof: ⁸

$$\begin{aligned}
valMeasTotalReward (p :: ps) x &= \\
&(val' (p :: ps) x) && \quad =\{\text{by definition of } val'\} = \\
&(meas (map sumR (trj (p :: ps) x))) && \quad =\{\text{by definition of } trj\} = \\
&(meas (map sumR (map consxy (mx' \gg\gg trjps)))) && \quad =\{\text{map preserves composition}\} =
\end{aligned}$$

⁸ We are very grateful to the anonymous reviewer who suggested an alternative proof for the induction step. The proof presented here is based on his proof, and his suggestions have lead to significantly weaker conditions on the measure and thus a stronger result.

1151 $(meas (map (sumR \circ consxy) (mx' \ggtrsim trjps)))$ = { by definition of $sumR$ }=
 1152 $(meas (map ((r \circ head) \oplus sumR) (mx' \ggtrsim trjps)))$ = { relation $bind/join$ }=
 1153 $(meas (map ((r \circ head) \oplus sumR) (join (map trjps mx'))))$ = { by $measAlgLemma$ }=
 1154 $(meas (map (meas \circ map (r \circ head \oplus sumR) \circ trjps) mx'))$ = { by $measSumLemma$ }=
 1155 $(meas (map (r \oplus meas \circ map sumR \circ trjps) mx'))$ = { by definition of val' }=
 1156 $(meas (map (r \oplus val' ps) mx'))$ = { by induction hypothesis }=
 1157 $(meas (map (r \oplus val ps) mx'))$ = { by definition of val }=
 1158 $(val (p :: ps) x)$

□

1161 **Technical remarks.** The above proof of $valMeasTotalReward$ omits some technical
 1162 details that may be uninteresting for a pen and paper proof, but turn out to be crucial
 1163 in the setting of an intensional type theory – like Idris – where function extensionality
 1164 does not hold in general. In particular, we have to postulate that the functorial map pre-
 1165 serves extensional equality (see Appendix 1.2 and (Botta *et al.*, *n.d.*)) for Idris to accept the
 1166 proof. In fact, most of the reasoning proceeds by replacing functions that are mapped onto
 1167 monadic values by other functions that are only extensionally equal. Using that map pre-
 1168 serves extensional equality allows to carry out such proofs generically without knowledge
 1169 of the concrete structure of the functor.

6.4 Correctness of monadic backward induction

1171 As corollary, we can now prove the correctness of monadic backward induction, namely
 1172 that the policy sequences computed by bi are optimal with respect to the measured total
 1173 reward computed by val' :

1174 $biOptMeasTotalReward : (t, n : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow GenOptPolicySeq\ val' (bi\ t\ n)$

1175 $biOptMeasTotalReward\ t\ n\ ps'\ x =$

1176 **let** $vvEqL = sym (valMeasTotalReward\ ps'\ x)$ **in**

1177 **let** $vvEqR = sym (valMeasTotalReward (bi\ t\ n)\ x)$ **in**

1178 **let** $biOpt = biOptVal\ t\ n\ ps'\ x$ **in**

1179 $replace\ vvEqR (replace\ vvEqL\ biOpt)$

7 Discussion

1181 In the last two sections we have seen what the three conditions mean for concrete examples
 1182 and how they are used in the correctness proof. In this section we take a step back and
 1183 consider them from a more abstract point of view.

1184 **Category-theoretical perspective.** Readers familiar with the theory of monads might
 1185 have recognised that the first two conditions ensure that $meas$ is the structure map of a
 1186 monad algebra for M on Val and thus the pair $(Val, meas)$ is an object of the Eilenberg-
 1187 Moore category associated with the monad M . The third condition requires the map $(v \oplus)$
 1188 to be an M -algebra homomorphism – a structure preserving map – for arbitrary values v .

This perspective allows us to use existing knowledge about monad algebras as a first criterion for choosing measures. For example, the Eilenberg-Moore-algebras of the list monad are monoids – this implicitly played a role in the examples we considered above. Jacobs (2011) shows that the algebras of the distribution monad for probability distributions with finite support correspond to convex sets. Interestingly, convex sets play an important role in the theory of optimal control (Bertsekas *et al.*, 2003).

Measures for the list monad. The knowledge that monoids are *List*-algebras suggests a generic description of admissible measures for $M = \text{List}$: Given a monoid (Val, \odot, b) , we can prove that monoid homomorphisms of the form $\text{foldr} \odot b$ fulfil the three conditions, if \oplus distributes over \odot on the left. I.e. for $\text{meas} = \text{foldr} \odot b$ the three conditions can be proven from

$$\begin{aligned} \text{odotNeutrRight} & : (l : \text{Val}) \quad \rightarrow l \odot \text{neutr} = l \\ \text{odotNeutrLeft} & : (r : \text{Val}) \quad \rightarrow \text{neutr} \odot r = r \\ \text{odotAssociative} & : (l, v, r : \text{Val}) \rightarrow l \odot (v \odot r) = (l \odot v) \odot r \\ \text{oplusOdDistrLeft} & : (n, l, r : \text{Val}) \rightarrow n \oplus (l \odot r) = (n \oplus l) \odot (n \oplus r) \end{aligned}$$

Neutrality of b on the right is needed for measPureSpec , while measJoinSpec follows from neutrality on the left and the associativity of \odot . The algebra morphism condition on $(v \oplus)$ is provable from the distributivity of \oplus over \odot and again neutrality of b on the right. If moreover \odot is monotone with respect to \sqsubseteq

$$\text{odotMon} : \{a, b, c, d : \text{Val}\} \rightarrow a \sqsubseteq b \rightarrow c \sqsubseteq d \rightarrow (a \odot c) \sqsubseteq (b \odot d)$$

then we can also prove measMonSpec using the transitivity of \sqsubseteq . The proofs are simple and can be found in the supplementary material to this paper. This also illustrates how the three abstract conditions follow from more familiar algebraic properties.

Mutual independence. Although it does not seem surprising, it should be noted that the three conditions are mutually independent. This can be concluded from the counter-examples in Sec. 5.1: The sum, the modified list maximum and the arithmetic average each fail exactly one of the three conditions.

Sufficient vs. necessary. The three conditions are sufficient to prove the extensional equality of the functions val and val' . They are justified by their level of generality and the fact that they hold for standard *measures* used in control theory. However, we leave open the interesting question whether these conditions are also necessary for the correctness of monadic backward induction.

Non-emptiness requirement. Note that mv in the premises of measPlusSpec is required to be non-empty. This condition arises from a pragmatic consideration. As an example, let us again use the list monad with $\text{Val} = \mathbb{N}$ and $\oplus = +$. It is not hard to see that for any natural number n greater than 0 the equality $\text{meas}(\text{map}(n+) []) = n + \text{meas} []$ must fail. So, if we wish to use the standard list data type instead of defining a custom type of non-empty lists, the only way to prove the base case of measPlusSpec is by contradiction with the non-emptiness premise.

1243 However, omitting the premise $mv : \text{NotEmpty}$ would not prevent us from generically
 1244 proving the correctness result of Section 6 – it would even simplify matters as it would
 1245 spare us reasoning about preservation of non-emptiness. But it would implicitly restrict the
 1246 class of monads that can be used to instantiate M . For example, we have seen above, that
 1247 measPlusSpec is not provable for the empty list without the non-emptiness premise and we
 1248 would therefore need to resort to a custom type of non-empty lists instead.

1249 The price to pay for including the non-emptiness premise is the additional condi-
 1250 tion nextNotEmpty on the transition function next that was already stated in Sec. 3.3.
 1251 Moreover, we have to postulate non-emptiness preservation laws for the monad operations
 1252 (Appendix 1.2) and to prove an additional lemma about the preservation of non-emptiness
 1253 (Appendix 4). Conceptually, it might seem cleaner to omit the non-emptiness condition: In
 1254 this case, the remaining conditions would only concern the interaction between the monad,
 1255 the measure, the type of values and the binary operation \oplus . However, the non-emptiness
 1256 preservation laws seem less restrictive with respect to the monad. In particular, for our
 1257 above example of ordinary lists they hold (the relevant proofs can be found in the supple-
 1258 mentary material). Thus we have opted for explicitly restricting the next function instead
 1259 of implicitly restricting the class of monads for which the result of Sec. 6 holds.

1260 8 Conclusion

1261 In this paper, we have proposed correctness criteria for monadic backward induction and
 1262 its underlying value function in the framework for specifying and solving finite-horizon,
 1263 monadic SDPs proposed in (Botta *et al.*, 2017a). After having shown that these criteria
 1264 are not necessarily met for arbitrary monadic SDPs, we have formulated three general
 1265 compatibility conditions. We have given a proof that monadic backward induction and its
 1266 underlying value function are correct if these conditions are fulfilled.

1267 The main theorem has been proved via the extensional equality of two functions: 1) the
 1268 value function of Bellman’s dynamic programming (Bellman, 1957) and optimal control
 1269 theory (Bertsekas, 1995; Puterman, 2014) that is also at the core of the generic backward
 1270 induction algorithm of (Botta *et al.*, 2017a) and 2) the measured total reward function
 1271 that specifies the objective of decision making in monadic SDPs: the maximisation of a
 1272 measure of the sum of the rewards along the trajectories rooted at the state associated with
 1273 the first decision.

1274 Our contribution to verified optimal decision making is twofold: On the one hand, we
 1275 have implemented a machine-checked generalisation of the semi-formal results for deter-
 1276 ministic and stochastic SDPs discussed in (Bertsekas, 1995, Prop. 1.3.1) and (Puterman,
 1277 2014, Theorem 4.5.1.c). As a consequence, we now have a provably correct method for
 1278 solving deterministic and stochastic sequential decision problems with their canonical
 1279 measure functions. On the other hand, we have identified three general conditions that
 1280 are sufficient for the equivalence between the two functions and thus the correctness result
 1281 to hold. The first two conditions are natural compatibility conditions between the measure
 1282 of uncertainty meas and the monadic operations associated with the uncertainty monad
 1283 M . The third condition is a distributivity principle concerning the relationship between
 1284 meas , the functorial map associated with M and the rule for adding rewards \oplus . All three
 1285
 1286
 1287
 1288

1289 conditions have a straightforward category-theoretical interpretation in terms of Eilenberg-
 1290 Moore algebras (MacLane, 1978, ch. VI.2). As discussed in Sec. 7, the three conditions
 1291 are independent and have non-trivial implications for the measure and the addition func-
 1292 tion that cannot be derived from the monotonicity condition on *meas* already imposed in
 1293 (Ionescu, 2009; Botta *et al.*, 2017a).

1294 A consequence of this contribution is more flexibility: We can now compute verified
 1295 solutions of stochastic sequential decision problems in which the measure of uncertainty is
 1296 different from the expected value measure. This is important for applications in which the
 1297 goal of decision making is, for example, of maximising the value of worst-case outcomes.
 1298 To the best of our knowledge, the formulation of the compatibility condition and the proof
 1299 of the equivalence between the two value functions are novel results.

1300 The latter can be employed in a wider context than the one that has motivated our study:
 1301 in many practical problems in science and engineering, the computation of optimal policies
 1302 via backward induction (let apart brute-force or gradient methods) is simply not feasible.
 1303 In these problems one often still needs to generate, evaluate and compare different policies
 1304 and our result shows under which conditions such evaluation can safely be done via the
 1305 “fast” value function *val* of standard control theory.

1306 Finally, our contribution is an application of verified, literal programming to optimal
 1307 decision making: the sources of this document have been written in literal Idris and are
 1308 available at (Brede & Botta, 2021), where the reader can also find the bare code and some
 1309 examples. Although the development has been carried out in Idris, it should be readily
 1310 reproducible in other implementations of type theory like Agda or Coq.

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 1324 sure function for the result to hold. This warrants the applicability of the Botta *et al.*
 1325 framework for verified decision making to a wider class of problems than our original
 1326 conditions.

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 1333

Conflicts of Interest

None.

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1394 Appendices

1395 1 Preliminaries

1396 1.1 General remarks concerning the Idris formalisation

- 1397
- 1398 • Idris’ type checker often struggles with dependencies in implicit arguments. We
 1399 sometimes use abbreviations to avoid cluttering the proofs with implicit arguments.
 - 1400 • As a standard, we write $(f \circ g \circ h) x$ instead of $f (g (h x))$.
 1401 When this is a problem for the type checker, we use the second notation.
 - 1402 • Functions that are not defined explicitly are from the Idris standard library.
 1403 Examples are *cong*, *void* and *concat*.
 - 1404 • Proofs in Idris can be implemented by preorder reasoning.
 1405 I.e. equational reasoning steps of the form

$$1406 \begin{array}{l} (t_1) = \{ \text{step} \} = \\ (t_2) \quad \square \end{array}$$

1407 as displayed in this appendix are actual type-checkable implementations of proofs.

1410 1.2 Monad Laws

1411 In the BJI-framework, M is required to be a *container monad* but none of the standard
 1412 monad laws (Bird, 2014) is required for the verification result to hold. By contrast, to prove
 1413 our extended correctness result, we need M to be a full-fledged monad. More specifically,
 1414 we require of the monad M that

- 1415 • it is equipped with functor and monad operations:

$$1416 \text{map} : \{A, B : \text{Type}\} \rightarrow (A \rightarrow B) \rightarrow M A \rightarrow M B$$

$$1417 \text{pure} : \{A : \text{Type}\} \rightarrow A \rightarrow M A$$

$$1418 (\gg) : \{A, B : \text{Type}\} \rightarrow M A \rightarrow (A \rightarrow M B) \rightarrow M B$$

$$1419 \text{join} : \{A : \text{Type}\} \rightarrow M (M A) \rightarrow M A$$

- 1420 • it preserves extensional equality (Botta *et al.*, *n.d.*), identity and composition of arrows:

1427 $mapPresEE : \{A, B : Type\} \rightarrow (f, g : A \rightarrow B) \rightarrow f \doteq g \rightarrow map f \doteq map g$

1428 $mapPresId : \{A : Type\} \rightarrow map id \doteq id$

1429 $mapPresComp : \{A, B, C : Type\} \rightarrow (f : A \rightarrow B) \rightarrow (g : B \rightarrow C) \rightarrow$

1430 $map (g \circ f) \doteq map g \circ map f$

- 1431 • Its *pure* and *join* operations are natural transformations (see MacLane, 1978, I.4):

1432 $pureNatTrans : \{A, B : Type\} \rightarrow (f : A \rightarrow B) \rightarrow map f \circ pure \doteq pure \circ f$

1433 $joinNatTrans : \{A, B : Type\} \rightarrow (f : A \rightarrow B) \rightarrow map f \circ join \doteq join \circ map (map f)$

1434 and fulfil the neutrality and associativity axioms:

1435 $pureNeutralLeft : \{A : Type\} \rightarrow join \circ pure \doteq id$

1436 $pureNeutralRight : \{A : Type\} \rightarrow join \circ map pure \doteq id$

1437 $joinAssoc : \{A : Type\} \rightarrow join \circ map join \doteq join \circ join$

1440 Notice that the above specification of the monad operations is not minimal: (\ggg) is not
 1441 assumed to be implemented in terms of *join* and *map* (or *map* and *join* via (\ggg) and *pure*).
 1442 Therefore (\ggg) (pronounced “bind”), *join* and *map* have to fulfil:

1443 $bindJoinSpec : \{A, B : Type\} \rightarrow (ma : M A) \rightarrow (f : A \rightarrow M B) \rightarrow (ma \ggg f) = join (map f ma)$

1444 The equality in the axioms is extensional equality, not the type theory’s definitional
 1445 equality:

1446 $(\doteq) : \{A, B : Type\} \rightarrow (f, g : A \rightarrow B) \rightarrow Type$

1447 $(\doteq) \{A\} f g = (a : A) \rightarrow f a = g a$

1448 As Idris does not have function extensionality, not postulating definitional equalities makes
 1449 the axioms strictly weaker.

1450 The BJI-framework also requires *M* to be equipped with type-level membership, with a
 1451 universal quantifier and with a type-valued predicate

1452 $NotEmpty : \{A : Type\} \rightarrow M A \rightarrow Type$

1453 For our purposes, the monad operations are moreover required to fulfil the following
 1454 preservation laws:

- 1455 • The *M*-structure obtained from lifting an element into the monad is not empty:

1456 $pureNotEmpty : \{A : Type\} \rightarrow (a : A) \rightarrow NotEmpty (pure a)$

- 1457 • The monad’s *map* and *bind* preserve non-emptiness:

1458 $mapPresNotEmpty : \{A, B : Type\} \rightarrow (f : A \rightarrow B) \rightarrow (ma : M A) \rightarrow$

1459 $NotEmpty ma \rightarrow NotEmpty (map f ma)$

1460 $bindPresNotEmpty : \{A, B : Type\} \rightarrow (f : A \rightarrow M B) \rightarrow (ma : M A) \rightarrow$

1461 $NotEmpty ma \rightarrow ((a : A) \rightarrow NotEmpty (f a)) \rightarrow NotEmpty (ma \ggg f)$

1462 As discussed in Sec. 7, we could have omitted these non-emptiness preservation laws,
 1463 but instead would have implicitly restricted the class of monads for which the correctness
 1464 result holds.

1.3 Preservation of extensional equality

We have stated above that for our correctness proof the functor M has to satisfy the monad laws and moreover its functorial *map* has to preserve extensional equality.

This e.g. is the case for $M = Identity$ (no uncertainty), $M = List$ (non-deterministic uncertainty) and for the finite probability distributions (stochastic uncertainty, $M = Prob$) discussed in (Botta *et al.*, 2017a). For $M = List$ the proof of *mapPresEE* amounts to:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{mapPresEE} &: \{A, B : \text{Type}\} \rightarrow (f, g : A \rightarrow B) \rightarrow f \doteq g \rightarrow \text{map}f \doteq \text{map}g \\
\text{mapPresEE } f \text{ } g \text{ } p \text{ } Nil &= \text{Refl} \\
\text{mapPresEE } f \text{ } g \text{ } p \text{ } (a :: as) &= \\
&(\text{map}f \text{ } (a :: as)) = \{\text{Refl}\} = \\
&(f \text{ } a :: \text{map}f \text{ } as) = \{\text{cong } \{f = \lambda x \Rightarrow x :: \text{map}f \text{ } as\} (p \text{ } a)\} = \\
&(g \text{ } a :: \text{map}f \text{ } as) = \{\text{cong } (\text{mapPresEE } f \text{ } g \text{ } p \text{ } as)\} = \\
&(g \text{ } a :: \text{map}g \text{ } as) = \{\text{Refl}\} = \\
&(\text{map}g \text{ } (a :: as)) \quad \square
\end{aligned}$$

The principle of extensional equality preservation is discussed in more detail in (Botta *et al.*, *n.d.*).

2 Correctness of the value function

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{valMeasTotalReward} &: \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow (ps : \text{PolicySeq } t \text{ } n) \rightarrow (x : X \text{ } t) \rightarrow \\
&\text{val}' \text{ } ps \text{ } x = \text{val} \text{ } ps \text{ } x
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{valMeasTotalReward } Nil \text{ } x &= \\
(\text{val}' \text{ } Nil \text{ } x) &= \{\text{Refl}\} = \\
(\text{meas} (\text{map} \text{ } \text{sumR} (\text{trj } Nil \text{ } x))) &= \{\text{Refl}\} = \\
(\text{meas} (\text{map} \text{ } \text{sumR} (\text{pure} (\text{Last } x)))) &= \{\text{cong } (\text{pureNatTrans } \text{sumR} (\text{Last } x))\} = \\
(\text{meas} (\text{pure} (\text{sumR} (\text{Last } x)))) &= \{\text{Refl}\} = \\
(\text{meas} (\text{pure } \text{zero})) &= \{\text{measPureSpec } \text{zero}\} = \\
(\text{zero}) &= \{\text{Refl}\} = \\
(\text{val } Nil \text{ } x) &\quad \square
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{valMeasTotalReward } \{t\} \{n = S \text{ } m\} (p :: ps) \text{ } x &= \\
\text{-- type abbreviations} & \\
\text{let } SCS &: \text{Type} = \text{StateCtrlSeq } (S \text{ } t) (S \text{ } m) & \text{in} \\
\text{let } SCS' &: \text{Type} = \text{StateCtrlSeq } t (S (S \text{ } m)) & \text{in} \\
\text{-- element and function abbreviations} & \\
\text{let } y &: Y \text{ } t \text{ } x = p \text{ } x & \text{in} \\
\text{let } mx' &: M (X (S \text{ } t)) = \text{next } t \text{ } x \text{ } y & \text{in} \\
\text{let } r &: (X (S \text{ } t) \rightarrow \text{Val}) = \text{reward } t \text{ } x \text{ } y & \text{in} \\
\text{let } \text{trjps} &: (X (S \text{ } t) \rightarrow M \text{ } SCS) = \text{trj } ps & \text{in} \\
\text{let } \text{consxy} &: (SCS \rightarrow SCS') = ((x ** y)##) & \text{in} \\
\text{let } mx' \text{ } \text{trjps} &: M \text{ } SCS = (mx' \gg= \text{trjps}) & \text{in} \\
\text{let } sR &: (SCS \rightarrow \text{Val}) = \text{sumR } \{t = S \text{ } t\} \{n = S \text{ } m\} & \text{in} \\
\text{let } hd &: (SCS \rightarrow X (S \text{ } t)) = \text{head } \{t = S \text{ } t\} \{n = m\} & \text{in} \\
\text{-- proof steps:} & \\
\text{let } \text{useMapPresComp} &= \text{mapPresComp } \text{consxy } \text{sumR } mx' \text{ } \text{trjps} & \text{in}
\end{aligned}$$

```

1519 let useBindJoinSpec = bindJoinSpec { B = SCS } trjps mx' in
1520 let useAlgLemma = algLemma { B = SCS }
1521           meas measJoinSpec
1522           ((r ◦ hd) ⊕ sumR) trjps mx' in
1523 let useMeasSumLemma = mapPresEE
1524           (meas ◦ map (r ◦ hd ⊕ sR) ◦ trjps)
1525           (r ⊕ meas ◦ map sR ◦ trjps)
1526           (measSumLemma ps r sR)
1527           mx' in
1528 let useIH = mapPresEE
1529           (r ⊕ val' ps)
1530           (r ⊕ val ps)
1531           (oplusLiftEERight (val' ps)
1532           (val ps) r (valMeasTotalReward ps))
1533           mx' in
1534 let ctx = λa ⇒ meas (map ((r ◦ hd) ⊕ sumR) a) in
1535 (val' (p :: ps) x) = { Refl } =
1536 (meas (map sumR (trj (p :: ps) x))) = { Refl } =
1537 (meas (map sumR (map consxy mx' trjps))) = { cong (sym useMapPresComp) } =
1538 (meas (map (sumR ◦ consxy) mx' trjps)) = { Refl } =
1539 (meas (map ((r ◦ hd) ⊕ sR) mx' trjps)) = { cong { f = ctx } useBindJoinSpec } =
1540 (meas (map ((r ◦ hd) ⊕ sR) (join (map trjps mx')))) = { sym useAlgLemma } =
1541 (meas (map (meas ◦ map (r ◦ hd ⊕ sR) ◦ trjps) mx')) = { cong useMeasSumLemma } =
1542 (meas (map (r ⊕ meas ◦ map sR ◦ trjps) mx')) = { Refl } =
1543 (meas (map (r ⊕ val' ps) mx')) = { cong useIH } =
1544 (meas (map (r ⊕ val ps) mx')) = { Refl } =
1545 (val (p :: ps) x)

```

□

3 Correctness of monadic backward induction

Together with the result of Botta *et al.* (*biOptVal*, see Appendix 6 below) we can prove the correctness of monadic backward induction as corollary, using a generalised optimality of policy sequences predicate:

$$\text{GenOptPolicySeq} : \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow (f : \text{PolicySeq } t \ n \rightarrow X \ t \rightarrow \text{Val}) \rightarrow \text{PolicySeq } t \ n \rightarrow \text{Type}$$

$$\text{GenOptPolicySeq } \{t\} \{n\} f \ ps = (ps' : \text{PolicySeq } t \ n) \rightarrow (x : X \ t) \rightarrow f \ ps' \ x \sqsubseteq f \ ps \ x$$

$$\text{biOptMeasTotalReward} : (t : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow (n : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \text{GenOptPolicySeq } \text{val}' \ (\text{bi } t \ n)$$

$$\text{biOptMeasTotalReward } t \ n \ ps' \ x =$$

```

1557 let vEqL = sym (valMeasTotalReward ps' x) in -- val' ps' x = val ps' x
1558 let vEqR = sym (valMeasTotalReward (bi t n) x) in -- val' (bi t n) x = val (bi t n) x
1559 let biOpt = biOptVal t n ps' x in -- val ps' x ⊆ val (bi t n) x
1560 let lP = λv ⇒ v ⊆ val (bi t n) x in
1561 let rP = λv ⇒ val' ps' x ⊆ v in

```

$$\text{replace } \{P = rP\} \text{vEqR } (\text{replace } \{P = lP\} \text{vEqL } \text{biOpt})$$

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4 Lemmas

The proof of *valMeasTotalReward* relies on a few auxiliary results which we prove here.

Lemma about the interaction of *head* and *trj* interleaved with *map*:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{headTrjLemma} : \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} &\rightarrow (ps : \text{PolicySeq } t \ n) \rightarrow \\ &(r : X \ t \rightarrow \text{Val}) \rightarrow (s : \text{StateCtrlSeq } t \ (S \ n) \rightarrow \text{Val}) \rightarrow (x' : X \ t) \rightarrow \\ &(\text{map } (r \circ \text{head} \oplus s) \circ \text{trj } ps) \ x' = (\text{map } (\text{const } (r \ x') \oplus s) \circ \text{trj } ps) \ x' \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{headTrjLemma } \{t\} \{n = Z\} \text{ Nil } r \ s \ x' =$$

```

let hd      = head {t}                in
let lastx'  = Last {t} x'            in
let nil     = Nil {t}                in
let usePureNatTrans = pureNatTrans (r ∘ hd ⊕ s) lastx' in
let usePureNatTransSym = sym (pureNatTrans ((⊕) (r x') ∘ s) lastx') in
  ((map (r ∘ hd ⊕ s)) (trj nil x'))      = { Refl } =
  ((map (r ∘ hd ⊕ s)) (pure lastx'))     = { usePureNatTrans } =
  ((pure ∘ (r ∘ hd ⊕ s)) lastx')         = { Refl } =
  ((pure ∘ (const (r x') ⊕ s)) lastx')   = { usePureNatTransSym } =
  (map (const (r x') ⊕ s) (pure lastx')) = { Refl } =
  (map (const (r x') ⊕ s) (trj nil x'))

```

□

$$\text{headTrjLemma } \{t = t\} \{n = S \ n\} (p :: ps) \ r \ s \ x' =$$

```

let y'      = p x'                in
let mx''    = next t x' y'        in
let SCS     = (StateCtrlSeq (S t) (S n)) in
let consx'y' = (##) {t} {n} (x' * y') in
let mx''trjps = (≫=) {B = SCS} mx'' (trj ps) in
let traj     = trj {t}            in
let useMapPresComp = mapPresComp consx'y' (const (r x') ⊕ s) mx''trjps in
let useMapPresCompSym = sym (mapPresComp consx'y' (r ∘ head ⊕ s) mx''trjps) in
  ((map (r ∘ head ⊕ s)) (traj (p :: ps) x'))      = { Refl } =
  ((map (r ∘ head ⊕ s) ∘ map consx'y') mx''trjps) = { useMapPresCompSym } =
  ((map ((r ∘ head ⊕ s) ∘ consx'y') mx''trjps)     = { Refl } =
  (map ((const (r x') ⊕ s) ∘ consx'y') mx''trjps) = { useMapPresComp } =
  (map (const (r x') ⊕ s) (map consx'y' mx''trjps)) = { Refl } =
  (map (const (r x') ⊕ s) (traj (p :: ps) x'))

```

□

Lemma about the commutation of *meas* ∘ *map* and \oplus :

$$\begin{aligned} \text{measSumLemma} : \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} &\rightarrow (ps : \text{PolicySeq } t \ n) \rightarrow \\ &(r : X \ t \rightarrow \text{Val}) \rightarrow \\ &(s : \text{StateCtrlSeq } t \ (S \ n) \rightarrow \text{Val}) \rightarrow \\ &(\text{meas} \circ \text{map } (r \circ \text{head} \oplus s) \circ \text{trj } ps) \doteq \\ &(r \oplus \text{meas} \circ \text{map } s \circ \text{trj } ps) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{measSumLemma } \{t\} \{n\} ps \ r \ s \ x' =$$

```

-- non-emptiness proofs
let trjNE      = trjNotEmptyLemma ps x' in

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```

1611 let sNE = mapPresNotEmpty s (trj ps x') trjNE in
-- proof steps
1612 let useMeasPlusSpec = measPlusSpec (r x') (map s (trj ps x')) sNE in
1613 let useMapPresComp = cong {f = \ prf => meas prf }
1614 (mapPresComp s ((r x') ⊕) (trj ps x')) in
1615 let useHdTrjLemma = cong (headTrjLemma ps r s x') in
1616 ((meas ∘ map (r ∘ head ⊕ s) ∘ trj ps) x') = { useHdTrjLemma } =
1617 ((meas ∘ map (const (r x') ⊕ s) ∘ trj ps) x') = { Refl } =
1618 ((meas ∘ map ((const (r x') ⊕ id) ∘ s) ∘ trj ps) x') = { useMapPresComp } =
1619 ((meas ∘ map (const (r x') ⊕ id) ∘ map s ∘ trj ps) x') = { Refl } =
1620 ((meas ∘ map ((r x') ⊕) ∘ map s ∘ trj ps) x') = { useMeasPlusSpec } =
1621 (((r x') ⊕) ∘ meas ∘ map s ∘ trj ps) x') = { Refl } =
1622 (((const (r x') ⊕ id) ∘ meas ∘ map s ∘ trj ps) x') = { Refl } =
1623 ((r ⊕ meas ∘ map s ∘ trj ps) x') □
1624

```

The *trj* function never produces an empty *M*-structure of trajectories:

```

1625
1626 trjNotEmptyLemma : { t, n : ℕ } → (ps : PolicySeq t n) → (x : X t) → NotEmpty (trj ps x)
1627
1628 trjNotEmptyLemma (Nil) x = pureNotEmpty (Last x)
1629 trjNotEmptyLemma { t = t } { n = S n } (p :: ps) x =
1630 let y = p x in
1631 let trjps = trj ps in
1632 let nxpx = next t x y in
1633 let consxy = ((x ** y)##) in
1634 let nne = nextNotEmpty x y in
1635 let netrjps = trjNotEmptyLemma ps in
1636 let bne = bindPresNotEmpty trjps nxpx nne netrjps in
mapPresNotEmpty consxy (nxpx >>= trjps) bne

```

A technical lemma to lift equalities into the right component of \oplus :

```

1637
1638 oplusLiftEERight : { A : Type } → (f, g, h : A → Val) → (g ≐ h) → (f ⊕ g) ≐ (f ⊕ h)
1639
1640 oplusLiftEERight { A } f g h ee a = cong (ee a)
1641
1642

```

4.1 Properties of monad algebras

Condition for a function *f* to be an *M*-algebra homomorphism:

```

1643
1644
1645
1646 algMorSpec : { A, B : Type } → (α : M A → A) → (β : M B → B) → (f : A → B) → Type
1647 algMorSpec { A } { B } α β f = (β ∘ map f) ≐ (f ∘ α)

```

Structure maps of *M*-algebras are left inverses of *pure*:

```

1648
1649
1650 algPureSpec : { A : Type } → (α : M A → A) → Type
1651 algPureSpec { A } α = α ∘ pure ≐ id

```

Structure maps of *M*-algebras are themselves *M*-algebra homomorphisms:

```

1652
1653
1654 algJoinSpec : { A : Type } → (α : M A → A) → Type
1655 algJoinSpec { A } α = algMorSpec join α α -- (α ∘ map α) ≐ (α ∘ join)

```

A lemma about computation with M -algebras:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{algLemma} : \{A, B, C : \text{Type}\} \rightarrow (\alpha : M C \rightarrow C) \rightarrow (ee : \text{algJoinSpec } \alpha) \rightarrow \\ (f : B \rightarrow C) \rightarrow (g : A \rightarrow M B) \rightarrow \\ (\alpha \circ \text{map } (\alpha \circ \text{map } f \circ g)) \doteq (\alpha \circ \text{map } f \circ \text{join} \circ \text{map } g) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{algLemma } \{A\} \{B\} \{C\} \alpha \text{ ee } f \text{ g } \text{ ma} = \\ ((\alpha \circ \text{map } (\alpha \circ \text{map } f \circ g)) \text{ ma}) &= \{ \text{cong } (\text{mapPresComp } g (\alpha \circ \text{map } f)) \text{ ma} \} = \\ ((\alpha \circ \text{map } (\alpha \circ \text{map } f) \circ \text{map } g) \text{ ma}) &= \{ \text{cong } (\text{mapPresComp } (\text{map } f) \alpha (\text{map } g \text{ ma})) \} = \\ ((\alpha \circ \text{map } \alpha \circ \text{map } (\text{map } f) \circ \text{map } g) \text{ ma}) &= \{ ee (\text{map } (\text{map } f) (\text{map } g \text{ ma})) \} = \\ ((\alpha \circ \text{join} \circ \text{map } (\text{map } f) \circ \text{map } g) \text{ ma}) &= \{ \text{cong } (\text{sym } (\text{joinNatTrans } f (\text{map } g \text{ ma}))) \} = \\ ((\alpha \circ \text{map } f \circ \text{join} \circ \text{map } g) \text{ ma}) & \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

4.2 Measure specifications

. The measure needs to be the structure map of an M -algebra on Val . This means:

- It is a left inverse to *pure*:

$$\text{measPureSpec} : \text{algPureSpec } \text{meas} \quad \text{-- } \text{meas} \circ \text{pure} \doteq \text{id}$$

- It is an M -algebra homomorphism from *join* to itself:

$$\text{measJoinSpec} : \text{algJoinSpec } \text{meas} \quad \text{-- } \text{meas} \circ \text{join} \doteq \text{meas} \circ \text{map } \text{meas}$$

Moreover, for all $v : \text{Val}$, the function $(v \oplus)$ needs to be an M -algebra homomorphism:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{measPlusSpec} : (v : \text{Val}) \rightarrow (mv : M \text{Val}) \rightarrow (\text{NotEmpty } mv) \rightarrow \\ (\text{meas} \circ \text{map } (v \oplus)) \text{ mv} = ((v \oplus) \circ \text{meas}) \text{ mv} \end{aligned}$$

We can omit the non-emptiness condition but this means we implicitly restrict the class of monads that can be used for M . The condition could then be expressed as

$$\text{measPlusSpec}' : (v : \text{Val}) \rightarrow \text{algMorSpec } \text{meas } \text{meas} (\oplus v)$$

5 Bellman's principle of optimality

Basic requirements for monadic backward induction:

$$(\sqsubseteq) : \text{Val} \rightarrow \text{Val} \rightarrow \text{Type}$$

$$\text{lteRefl} \quad : \{a : \text{Val}\} \rightarrow a \sqsubseteq a$$

$$\text{lteTrans} \quad : \{a, b, c : \text{Val}\} \rightarrow a \sqsubseteq b \rightarrow b \sqsubseteq c \rightarrow a \sqsubseteq c$$

$$\text{plusMonSpec} : \{a, b, c, d : \text{Val}\} \rightarrow a \sqsubseteq b \rightarrow c \sqsubseteq d \rightarrow (a \oplus c) \sqsubseteq (b \oplus d)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{measMonSpec} : \{A : \text{Type}\} \rightarrow (f, g : A \rightarrow \text{Val}) \rightarrow ((a : A) \rightarrow (f a) \sqsubseteq (g a)) \rightarrow \\ (\text{ma} : M A) \rightarrow \text{meas } (\text{map } f \text{ ma}) \sqsubseteq \text{meas } (\text{map } g \text{ ma}) \end{aligned}$$

Optimality of policy sequences:

1703 $OptPolicySeq : \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow PolicySeq\ t\ n \rightarrow Type$
 1704 $OptPolicySeq\ \{t\}\ \{n\}\ ps = (ps' : PolicySeq\ t\ n) \rightarrow (x : Xt) \rightarrow val\ ps'\ x \sqsubseteq val\ ps\ x$

1705 Optimality of extensions of policy sequences:

1706 $OptExt : \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow PolicySeq\ (St)\ n \rightarrow Policy\ t \rightarrow Type$
 1707 $OptExt\ \{t\}\ ps\ p = (p' : Policy\ t) \rightarrow (x : Xt) \rightarrow val\ (p' :: ps)\ x \sqsubseteq val\ (p :: ps)\ x$

1708 Bellman's principle of optimality:

1709 $Bellman : \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow (ps : PolicySeq\ (St)\ n) \rightarrow OptPolicySeq\ ps \rightarrow$
 1710 $(p : Policy\ t) \rightarrow OptExt\ ps\ p \rightarrow OptPolicySeq\ (p :: ps)$

1711 $Bellman\ \{t\}\ ps\ ops\ p\ oep\ (p' :: ps')\ x =$

1712 **let** y' = $p'\ x$ **in**
 1713 **let** mx' = $next\ t\ x\ y'$ **in**
 1714 **let** f' = $reward\ t\ x\ y' \oplus val\ ps'$ **in**
 1715 **let** f = $reward\ t\ x\ y' \oplus val\ ps$ **in**
 1716 **let** s_0 = $\lambda x' \Rightarrow plusMonSpec\ lteRefl\ (ops\ ps'\ x')$ **in**
 1717 **let** $s1$ = $measMonSpec\ f'\ f\ s_0\ mx'$ **in** -- $val\ (p' :: ps')\ x \sqsubseteq val\ (p' :: ps)\ x$
 1718 **let** $s2$ = $oep\ p'\ x$ **in** -- $val\ (p' :: ps)\ x \sqsubseteq val\ (p :: ps)\ x$
 1719 $lteTrans\ s1\ s2$

1724 6 Verification with respect to val

1725 The empty policy sequence is optimal:

1726 $nilOptPolicySeq : OptPolicySeq\ Nil$
 1727 $nilOptPolicySeq\ Nil\ x = lteRefl$

1728 Now, provided that we can implement

1729 $optExt : \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow PolicySeq\ (St)\ n \rightarrow Policy\ t$
 1730 $optExtSpec : \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow (ps : PolicySeq\ (St)\ n) \rightarrow OptExt\ ps\ (optExt\ ps)$

1731 then

1732 $bi : (t : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow (n : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow PolicySeq\ t\ n$
 1733 $bi\ t\ Z = Nil$
 1734 $bi\ t\ (Sn) = \mathbf{let}\ ps = bi\ (St)\ n\ \mathbf{in}\ optExt\ ps :: ps$

1735 is correct with respect to val :

1736 $biOptVal : (t : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow (n : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow OptPolicySeq\ (bi\ t\ n)$

1737 $biOptVal\ t\ Z = nilOptPolicySeq$
 1738 $biOptVal\ t\ (Sn) =$

1739 **let** ps = $bi\ (St)\ n$ **in**
 1740 **let** ops = $biOptVal\ (St)\ n$ **in**
 1741 **let** p = $optExt\ ps$ **in**
 1742 **let** oep = $optExtSpec\ ps$ **in**
 1743 $Bellman\ ps\ ops\ p\ oep$

7 Optimal extension

The generic implementation of backward induction bi naturally raises the question under which conditions one can implement $optExt$ such that $optExtSpec$ holds.

To this end, consider the function

$$\begin{aligned} cval &: \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow PolicySeq(S t) n \rightarrow (x : X t) \rightarrow Y t x \rightarrow Val \\ cval \{t\} ps x y &= \mathbf{let} \ mx' = next \ t \ x \ y \ \mathbf{in} \\ &\quad meas \ (map \ (reward \ t \ x \ y \oplus val \ ps) \ mx') \end{aligned}$$

By definition of val and $cval$, one has

$$\begin{aligned} val \ (p :: ps) \ x &= \\ &= meas \ (map \ (reward \ t \ x \ (p \ x) \oplus val \ ps) \ (next \ t \ x \ (p \ x))) \\ &= \\ cval \ ps \ x \ (p \ x) \end{aligned}$$

This suggests that, if we can maximise $cval$, i.e. implement

$$\begin{aligned} cvalmax &: \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow PolicySeq(S t) n \rightarrow (x : X t) \rightarrow Val \\ cvalargmax &: \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow PolicySeq(S t) n \rightarrow (x : X t) \rightarrow Y t x \end{aligned}$$

that fulfil

$$\begin{aligned} cvalmaxSpec &: \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow (ps : PolicySeq(S t) n) \rightarrow (x : X t) \rightarrow \\ &\quad (y : Y t x) \rightarrow cval \ ps \ x \ y \sqsubseteq cvalmax \ ps \ x \\ cvalargmaxSpec &: \{t, n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow (ps : PolicySeq(S t) n) \rightarrow (x : X t) \rightarrow \\ &\quad cvalmax \ ps \ x = cval \ ps \ x \ (cvalargmax \ ps \ x) \end{aligned}$$

then we can implement optimal extensions of arbitrary policy sequences. As it turns out, this intuition is correct. With

$$optExt = cvalargmax$$

one has

$$\begin{aligned} optExtSpec \ \{t\} \ \{n\} \ ps \ p' \ x &= \\ \mathbf{let} \ p &= optExt \ ps \ \mathbf{in} \\ \mathbf{let} \ y &= p \ x \ \mathbf{in} \\ \mathbf{let} \ y' &= p' \ x \ \mathbf{in} \\ \mathbf{let} \ s1 &= cvalmaxSpec \ ps \ x \ y' \ \mathbf{in} \\ \mathbf{let} \ s2 &= replace \ \{P = \lambda z \Rightarrow (cval \ ps \ x \ y' \sqsubseteq z)\} \ (cvalargmaxSpec \ ps \ x) \ s1 \ \mathbf{in} \\ &\quad s2 \end{aligned}$$

The observation that functions $cvalmax$ and $cvalargmax$ that fulfil $cvalmaxSpec$ and $cvalargmaxSpec$ are sufficient to implement an optimal extension $optExt$ that fulfils $optExtSpec$ naturally raises the question of what are necessary and sufficient conditions for $cvalmax$ and $cvalargmax$. Answering this question necessarily requires discussing properties of $cval$ and goes well beyond the scope of formulating a theory of SDPs. Here, we limit ourselves to remark that if $Y t x$ is finite and non-empty one can implement the functions $cvalmax$ and $cvalargmax$ by linear search. A generic implementation of $cvalmax$ and $cvalargmax$ can be found under (Brede & Botta, 2021).

For the original BJI-theory, tabulated backward induction and several example applications can be found in the *SequentialDecisionProblems* folder of (Botta, 2016–2021).